

**On-Demand Resource Allocation
Framework for Electric Vehicle
Enabled Microgrids**

by

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Declaration of Authorship

I, Ifiok Anthony Umoren, declare that this thesis titled, ‘On-Demand Resource Allocation Framework for Electric Vehicle Enabled Microgrids’ and the work presented in it are my own. I confirm that:

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- Where any part of this thesis has previously been submitted for a degree or any other qualification at this University or any other institution, this has been clearly stated.
- Where I have consulted the published work of others, this is always clearly attributed.
- Where I have quoted from the work of others, the source is always given. With the exception of such quotations, this thesis is entirely my own work.
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Abstract

Electric vehicles (EVs) are important distributed energy resources (DERs) for improving the greenness of power generation and reducing emissions. Under vehicle-to-grid (V2G) concept, EVs can be deployed to absorb excess production or feed-back surplus energy to the grid during peak demand or system failure. In this thesis, the electric vehicle as a service (EVaaS) framework is introduced, where EVs distributed over the local region are chosen, individually or in aggregate, to fulfil the energy demand of critical load (CL). CLs are facilities that need to be operating during prolong outages such as hospitals, care homes, residential houses with life support equipment, emergency shelters, evacuation centres and communication infrastructure. Three main work packages have been reported. Firstly, an auction scheme is designed for incentivized energy trading between EVs and CL. In the proposed setup, EV-CL association and discharging scheduling are considered in a two-phase model, where EV-CL association is modelled as a single auction to determine the winning bids and corresponding payments, while EV discharging scheduling is formulated as an operating cost minimization problem. The proposed scheme was shown to achieve comparable performance with reference schemes, guarantee bidder satisfaction and validate theoretical analysis on auction properties. Secondly, a combined economic emission model is proposed where both energy costs and carbon emissions are considered. The model is formulated as a bi-objective optimization problem, with carbon price as the weighting factor. The approach has been extended to evaluate the trade-off between EVaaS and conventional DERs. The greenness and effectiveness of the scheme is demonstrated. Thirdly, a resource efficiency model is proposed to optimize energy cost and radio resource usage in V2G communication networks, where EVs within a specific region are served by a base station and associated with CLs. As the proposed problem is inherently non-convex and known to be NP-hard, a suboptimal scheme is developed based on a two-phase algorithm. Phase 1 derives optimum EV-CL association using a heuristic approach, while phase

2 finds optimum power allocation using geometric programming. The sub-optimal scheme yields a performance close to the optimal solution, while its complexity is relatively low, making it promising for V2G applications.

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List of Abbreviations

5G	Fifth generation cellular network technology
AMI	Advanced Metering Infrastructure
BPP	Binomial Point Process
BS	Base Station
CE	Cost Efficiency
CEE	Combined Economic Emission
CL	Critical Load
DER	Distributed Energy Resource
DoD	Depth of Discharge
DG	Diesel Generator
ESS	Energy Storage System
EU ETS	European Union Emission Trading System
EV	Electric Vehicle
EVaaS	Electric Vehicle as a Service
EVSE	Electric Vehicle Supply Equipment
FCFS	First Come First Served
G2V	Grid-to-Vehicle
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GP	Geometric Programming
GRA	Greedy Algorithm
HGV	Heavy Good Vehicle

ICE	Internal Combustion Engine
ILP	Integer Linear Programming
IoT	Internet of Things
KPA	Knapsack Algorithm
MEG	Mobile Emergency Generator
MGCC	Microgrid Central Controller
MILP	Mixed Integer Linear Programming
MINLP	Mixed Integer Non-linear Programming
NLP	Non-linear Programming
OFDMA	Orthogonal Frequency-Division Multiple Access
PHEV	Plug-in Hybrid Electric Vehicle
RDR	Remaining Driving Range
RE	Resource Efficiency
RES	Renewable Energy Resource
RRM	Radio Resource Management
SE	Spectral Efficiency
SNR	Signal-to-Noise Ratio
SoC	State of Charge
V2G	Vehicle-to-Grid
V2V	Vehicle-to-Vehicle
V2X	Vehicle-to-Everything
VCG	Vickrey-Clarke-Grove

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Distributed Energy Resources (DER) form an important part of modern energy systems and is one that will grow as we move towards a more climate-friendly environment. DER refers to electric power generation and storage resources deployed across the distribution grid, typically close to load, which can be used individually or in aggregate to provide value to the grid, individual customers, or both. DER possess the potential to significantly enhance the overall performance of the electricity grid. However, the greater extent of virtual and physical interconnection, unfortunately leads to the cost of vulnerability to accidental failures and malicious attacks. Moreover, natural disasters such as the 2017 Storm Ophelia [1] and Hurricanes Maria, Irma, and Harvey [2] can also cause prolonged power outages, possibly affecting millions of lives and leading to public safety and economic disaster. It is anticipated that the frequency of occurrence will increase due to aging infrastructure and climate change [3].

Power systems must not only operate reliably during normal conditions, in response to known threats, but must be resilient, in response to unforeseeable contingencies [4]. There is heightened awareness that one of the essential components of resilience is the need to keep critical facilities operating during prolonged grid outages. For these reasons, it is important to explore the possible options on how to optimise energy distribution and smartly distribute the existing energy produced or stored in the local region. This will include reviewing existing emergency response plans, mapping out critical facilities within the region and identifying critical loads (CLs). Emergency control centres, evacuation and emergency shelters, hospitals, communication infrastructures, security infrastructures and airports are considered as critical loads. The best way to manage distribution is to divide the distribution system into small clusters or microgrids, interconnected through regional data centre to ensure exchanges and coordination.

Microgrid as an essential part of smart grids, manages electricity demand and provides support intended to increase the dependability and efficiency of the system. Unfortunately, until key grid needs; greener, more reliable and more resilient, are satisfied, microgrids would not be an integral part of the electricity generation reform. The global push to rely more on renewable energy sources (RESs) is motivated by the clean-energy transition. RESs reduces greenhouse gas emission and enables economic benefits for both utilities and customers. However, RESs are intermittent and limited, based on heterogeneous technologies with unique characteristics and have less capacity compared to conventional power sources [5]. Electric vehicles (EVs) can help improve the grid capabilities to handles RESs by providing ancillary services, either via charging or discharging [6]. Vehicle-to-grid (V2G) concept enables EVs to be deployed to absorb excess production or feed-back surplus energy to

the distribution grid during peak demand or system failure [7]. However, effective integration, coordination and control of these new technologies remain a great challenge.

1.2 Problem Statements

In this thesis, several research problems related to resource optimisation in electric vehicle enabled microgrids were discussed.

Auction Model for Incentivized Energy Trading: Several auction mechanisms have been developed and applied in the literature to a wide range of V2G energy trading applications [8–15]. However, there is a lack of auction models that consider EV mobility and battery degradation. Additionally, bidder satisfaction has not been studied in the literature. This model could incentivize EV participation in energy trading and ensure EV owners are not subjected to unfair trade conditions.

Model for Combined Economic Emission Based Association: Several studies have exploited EVs as fixed energy storage unit involving unit commitment model and solve an economic/emission dispatch problem [16–19]. However, there is limited study that exploits physically distant EVs to provide capacity on-demand to fulfil CL demand in microgrids. This model could offer guidance on finding the optimal association of physically distant EVs with CL, towards reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions.

Model for Radio Resource Management in V2G Communication Networks: Several studies have focused on V2G communication that enable EVs and microgrid interaction for EV charging management [20–27]. However, there is a lack of model for managing the radio resources of discharging EVs in the distribution grid. Thus, this model will help in the selection of

suitable EVs with efficient communication links and operating costs to fulfil CL demand.

1.3 Research Questions

The research questions addressed in this thesis are as follows.

- How can EVs improve the flexibility of the conventional energy market?
- What effect does increased charge cycle of EV batteries due to V2G have on the EV owners?
- How can EV owners be incentivized to trade energy in decentralised V2G environment?
- How effective are V2G-enabled EVs at reducing GHG emissions?
- How can radio resources be maximised in V2G communication networks?

1.4 Research Objectives

The aim of the research is to design a novel energy management framework that improves distribution system efficiency using EVs. The framework is based on an electric vehicle as a service (EVaaS) model, which exploits physically distant EVs within the microgrid to significantly enhance the overall performance of the distribution system. The objectives of the research are:

- Develop a novel on-demand energy management framework for electric vehicle enabled microgrids.

- Develop an auction model for incentivized energy trading in decentralised V2G environment.
- Develop a combined economic emission model that considers energy cost and carbon emission in centralised V2G environment.
- Develop a resource efficiency model that jointly considers energy cost and radio usage in V2G communication networks.

1.5 Contributions and Publications

The contribution of this study can be summarised as follows.

- The EVaaS framework and inherent challenges associated with the deployment of EVs for outage mitigation and balancing short-term demand-supply mismatch have been introduced and discussed. This reveals that EVs can be used, individually or in aggregate, as DERs to be allocated in distribution systems.
- An auction scheme is designed for a one-sided market where EVs within the microgrid are competing to sell their surplus energy. EVs are motivated to participate in the market via several incentives, most notably bidder satisfaction, transportation cost and battery degradation cost. Bidder satisfaction guarantees that EVs would not experience inconveniences beyond their user-specified levels.
- Carbon emission minimisation has been considered alongside economic benefit maximisation to develop a combined economic emission optimisation model for EVs in a microgrid. The model further integrates EV battery capacity loss and degradation cost, so they do not become financial liabilities of EV owners.

- A resource efficiency optimisation model that jointly considers energy cost and radio usage in V2G communication networks has been proposed. The resource efficiency exploits the trade-off between spectral efficiency and cost efficiency for EVs balancing demand of CL in a microgrid.

This study has produced the following publications:

Peer-reviewed Journal Papers

- [1] I. Umoren and M. Shakir, “Electric vehicle as a service (EVaaS): Applications, challenges and enablers,” *Energies*, 2022, vol. 15, no. 19, pp. 7207, Sept. 2022. (Chapter 2)
- [2] I. Umoren, M. Shakir and H. Tabassum, “Resource efficient vehicle-to-grid (V2G) communication systems for electric vehicle enabled microgrids,” *Trans. Intell. Transp. Syst.*, vol. 22, no. 7, pp. 4171-4180, Jul. 2021. (Chapter 4)
- [3] I. Umoren and M. Shakir, “Combined economic emission based resource allocation for electric vehicle enabled microgrids,” *IET Smart Grid*, vol. 3, no. 6, pp. 768–776, Dec. 2020. (Chapter 5)
- [4] I. Umoren, S. Jaffary, M. Shakir, K. Katzis, and H. Ahmadi, “Blockchain-based energy trading in electric vehicle enabled microgrids,” *IEEE Consum. Electron. Mag.*, vol. 9, no. 6, pp. 66–71, Nov. 2020.
- [5] I. Umoren, M. Shakir and H. Ahmadi, “VCG-based auction for incentivized energy trading in electric vehicle enabled microgrids,” *IEEE Access*, (Submitted). (Chapter 3)

Peer-reviewed Conference Papers

- [1] I. Umoren and M. Shakir, "EVaaS: A novel on-demand outage mitigation framework for electric vehicle enabled microgrids," in *Proc. IEEE Globecom Workshops (GC Wkshps)*, Abu Dhabi, UAE, 9-13 Dec. 2018.

FIGURE 1.1: Thesis structure showing the summary of the chapters.

1.6 Organisation of the Thesis

Figure 1.1 provides an overview of the thesis structure showing the relationship among the chapters. A brief summary of the chapters is given below:

Chapter 2 presents the EVaaS framework used in the thesis and system requirements needed for the successful deployment of EVs for grid-related services. The EVaaS architecture and communication infrastructure for EV-enabled microgrids are discussed. Several market designs and mechanisms that incentivize EV participation in EVaaS are also discussed. Benefits and challenges associated with EV deployment in EV-enabled microgrids are evaluated. The EVaaS framework achieves the first objective of the thesis. Based on the EVaaS framework, three aspects of EV deployment are investigated in Chapters 3, 4 and 5: economic, emissions and communications, respectively.

Chapter 3 presents an auction mechanism for a one-sided market where EVs within the microgrid are competing to sell their surplus energy to the CL. Successful bidders are determined by solving a mixed integer non-linear programming (MINLP) problem, which is subject to practical constraints such as energy demand and charging station limit. Vickery-Clarke-Groves payment rule was applied to pay the auction winners. EV discharging scheduling is formulated as an operating cost minimisation problem. Numerical results reveal that the proposed scheme achieves comparable performance with reference schemes, guarantees bidder satisfaction and validates theoretical analysis on auction properties. This model achieves the second objective of the thesis.

Chapter 4 presents a combined economic emission optimisation model for EV-CL association in the microgrid. The economic aspect in Chapter 3 is examined alongside the emissions aspect to propose an optimisation model for energy cost and carbon emission reductions, considering carbon price of

emission. EV battery capacity loss and degradation cost are analysed to ensure it does not deter EV participation in EVaaS. The trade-off between EVaaS and conventional DERs is evaluated. The feasibility of the proposed model is demonstrated in simulation studies and numerical results demonstrate the efficacy of the proposed resource allocation scheme. This model achieves the third objective of the thesis.

Chapter 5 presents a resource efficiency framework that exploits the trade-off between spectral efficiency and cost efficiency of EVs in V2G communication networks. Here, the economic aspect in Chapter 3 is examined through cost efficiency. As the resource efficiency problem is inherently non-convex and known to be NP-hard, a suboptimal scheme is developed. Upper and lower bounds to the optimal resource efficiency are then derived as a benchmark to study the performance gap of the suboptimal scheme. Simulation results demonstrate that the proposed suboptimal scheme is close to the optimal solution, while its complexity is relatively low, making it promising for V2G applications. This model achieves the fourth objective of the thesis.

Chapter 6 presents a conclusion to the work described in this thesis. The contributions are summarised, followed by suggestions regarding directions of future research related to this work.

Chapter 2

Background and Related Work

2.1 Introduction

This chapter introduces the electric vehicle as a service (EVaaS) framework where suitable electric vehicles (EVs) within the distribution network are chosen individually or in aggregate to exchange energy with the grid or critical loads. It studies the interactions among EVaaS subsystems such as EV battery, charging station, load and communication infrastructure. It also provides background information essential to understanding the models developed in later chapters, as well as a review of recent relevant work found in literature. This chapter is based on [28] and addresses the first research question of this thesis.

Due to climate change, fossil energy reserves and greenhouse gas (GHG) emission concerns, efforts are currently going towards the transition to electric mobility [29]. There are several kinds of government policies designed to reduce GHG emissions and promote the acceptance of EVs, such as the Accelerating to Zero (A2Z) coalition launched at the 27th Conference of the

Parties (COP27) [30], UK's zero emission vehicle mandate [31], California's zero emission vehicle package [32], China's new energy vehicle (NEV) mandate [33] and the Corporate Average Fuel Economy (CAFE) standards [34]. There are also government incentives designed to support policy-driven adoption of EVs, such as purchase rebates, tax credits, tax exemptions, and waivers on charging and parking fees. However, due to social obstacles, technical limitations and cost premiums compared to conventional internal combustion engine (ICE) vehicles, EVs have not been widely adopted [35]. The main types of EVs on the market are battery electric vehicles (BEV), plug-in hybrid electric vehicles (PHEVs), extended range electric vehicle (EREVs) and fuel cell vehicles (FCVs) [36]. For purposes of the thesis, all electric vehicles with plug-in capabilities are collectively referred to as "EVs".

Range anxiety - fears over the distance EVs can travel between charges - is a major technological barrier to large-scale adoption of EVs [37]. One of the factors influencing range anxiety is the availability of EV charging points. Fears over lack of charging points was identified in [38] as the biggest concern with regards to EV ownership. However, with several government policies across the globe supporting the increased penetration of EVs [39], there has been a rapid rise in the number of charge points. The remaining driving range (RDR) - distance an EV can travel with the residual energy in the battery - is another factor influencing range anxiety. The RDR of EVs cannot be accurately estimated by current technologies; hence, drivers tend to reserve around 30% of battery capacity as an emergency buffer, to protect them from running out of power [40]. With accurate RDR estimation, drivers would be able to make efficient use of their limited battery capacity, thereby minimising range anxiety considerably [41]

Known for their features as energy-conserving and emission free, EVs have become the future trend. EVs have advantages over ICE vehicles, most notably

the ability to be used as a service for the electricity grid - EVaaS. EVs can provide service individually or as part of an aggregation. In the later, EVs are selected into groups by aggregators, to create a larger, more manageable capacity or load for the electricity grid [42]. EVs receive power from the grid to charge their batteries in grid-to-vehicle (G2V) mode, whereas in vehicle-to-grid (V2G) mode, EVs supply part of their stored energy back to the grid. We use the term “V2G” to broadly refer to both G2V (unidirectional) and V2G (bidirectional) energy flows in this thesis. Although the concept of V2G was introduced over two decades ago [7], it is still in the very early stages of development. There are different versions of V2G characterised by their energy exchange processes such as vehicle-to-home (V2H), vehicle-to-building (V2B) and vehicle-to-vehicle (V2V). V2H is a small-scale version of V2G which allows an EV to supply homes with the energy stored in its battery [43]. Similar to V2H, V2B allows EVs to power buildings [44], whereas V2V involves energy exchange between EVs in social hotspots such as charging stations, parking lots and swapping stations [45].

In V2G concept, EVs are integrated into the electricity grid, where energy is first stored in the EV battery and then fed back into the grid. In [46], the technical, commercial and domestic proposition of V2G technology to the distribution network is evaluated through demonstrator projects. From a utility perspective, there are numerous economic benefits from V2G. These include ancillary services such as energy balancing, voltage and frequency regulation, active and reactive power support, current harmonic filtering, spinning reserves, valley filling, peak shaving and load following. V2G can also improve the technical performance of the electricity grid in areas such as stability, reliability, efficiency and resilience. V2G can further reduce emissions, replace large-scale energy storage systems, improve load factors, provide support for renewable energy sources (RESs), and by contributing to local consumption,

could reduce electricity transport losses in grids with high penetration of decentralised generation. Additionally, the savings in utility operations will minimise the overall service cost to customers, which will be reflected in energy prices. The aforementioned benefits are not specific to either G2V or V2G alone, but true of V2G in general.

While the potential benefits of V2G transition have been widely recognised, they may not accrue without significant challenges. Impediments to V2G actualisation include resistance from automotive and oil sectors, communication infrastructure needed for information exchange, battery degradation, requirements for monetisation of energy losses, and technical, political, social and cultural obstacles. EV battery degradation costs happens to be one of the main barriers to V2G transition. An additional issue is that energy flow will become bidirectional and increasingly complex. Since the distribution grid has not been designed for this purpose, service capabilities of V2G devices tend to be limited. Conversely, bidirectional communications implementation in V2G infrastructures unlocks new possible vulnerabilities.

The implementation impact of V2G technologies on the distribution system and strategies for V2G interfaces for individual and aggregated EVs were studied in [47]. The study in [48] discussed the operation of EVs and their impact on grid stability. The methodology adopted for power flow under V2G scheme and challenges associated with the commercial level adoption of V2G are described in [49]. The study in [50] assess the long-term viability of V2G in a flexible energy system in the UK. In [51], around 320 domestic V2G charge points were installed in the UK and a trial was conducted to demonstrate the commercial viability of V2G at a residential level. The study validates the business case of residential customers participating and benefiting from providing V2G services. The study in [52] inspects the implementation challenges of EVs infrastructural and charging systems in conjunction with several

international standards and charging codes. The ancillary service potential of V2G is presented in [53] and the potential impacts, challenges and future market penetration capabilities of V2G technology is discussed. Several studies have been conducted to evaluate the impacts of V2G integration on the utility. However, little attention has been given to maximising the full potentials of V2G from an EV-prosumer perspective. The technologies, technical components and system requirements needed for the deployment of EVs for grid-related services are reviewed in this chapter. The system architecture and communication infrastructure for EV-enabled microgrids are introduced. The market design and various mechanisms that motivate EV owners to participate in energy trading are discussed. Optimisation methods for EV charging/discharging, and benefits and barriers to the deployment of EVs are presented and evaluated.

2.2 Overview of EVaaS

2.2.1 EVaaS Framework

EVaaS describes a system in which heterogeneous electric vehicles communicate with the electricity grid to participate in grid-related services [54, 55]. EVaaS exploits V2G technology to develop a system where suitable EVs within the distribution network are chosen individually or in aggregate to exchange energy with the grid or individual customer, or both. It provides the opportunity for EV owners to benefit from an additional revenue stream. EV owners can be incentivised to charge their EV batteries when the energy generated exceeds demand, example, too much energy being generated from RESs or off-peak hours. By contrast, EV owners who self-generate electricity from RESs or connect to the grid to charge at low-demand, cheap tariff, can then market

the excess or unneeded energy stored in their EV batteries when energy costs are higher or during peak demand. Thus, EVs can act as an energy reserve for the grid. The operation of EVaaS system is a distinctive combination of EV, an energy management system and a service contract which can deliver value by providing demand response services.

EV owners can go into a contract or agreement with the utility to make charging and discharging controlled, coordinated and more predictable. The utility can offer lower energy price to incentivize EV charging and battery insurance or maintenance service to incentivize EV discharging in exchange for EV owners agreeing to charge and discharge the battery, respectively, to meet the grid requirements. Based on this approach, the implementation of a centralised charging and discharging solution becomes feasible, as well as the possibility of maximising system efficiency. Alternatively, EV owners can voluntarily participate in EVaaS without making commitment with the utility. Different incentives can be offered by the utility to motivate the EV owners to charge or discharge their batteries, depending on the current demand and supply of the grid. The EV owners will individually consider their charging or discharging options in a distributed fashion. Based on this approach, a decentralised charging and discharging solution can achieve maximum system efficiency.

2.2.2 EVaaS Architecture

The architecture of an EVaaS system with interactions among subsystems is shown in Figure 2.1. The EVaaS system typically consists of EVs, loads (critical and non-critical), charging stations, smart meters, power lines, communication infrastructure and microgrid control centre or aggregators [42]. The system is remotely monitored and controlled by the microgrid control centre

FIGURE 2.1: EVaaS system architecture.

using a supervisory control and data acquisition (SCADA) system, while the subsystems communicate with each other through a communication network to effectively carry out tasks and collectively achieve an objective. The communication network facilitates the collection of necessary data from EVaaS subsystems and allows the aggregator to efficiently optimise EV charging and discharging. However, this is dependent on status monitoring and information update of both parked and moving EVs. The information includes the current location of EV or where it will be in the next time frame, battery capacity and state of charge (SOC). Using this information, the aggregator can forecast or estimate the energy demand or supply from EVs within a specific region.

TABLE 2.1: Overview of different EV passenger model battery features.

EV Model	Battery Technology	Capacity	Charge Times (100% charge in AC, 80% charge in DC)
Nissan Leaf e+ Tekna [56]	Li-ion	62 kWh	11.5 hrs on 7 kW AC charge 1.5 hrs on 50 kW DC charge
BMW i4 [57]	Li-ion	42 kWh	6 hrs on 7.4 kW AC charge 42 mins on 50 kW DC charge
Audi e-tron [58]	Li-ion	95 kWh	13.5 hrs on 7.4 kW AC charge 30 mins on 150 kW DC charge
Chevrolet Bolt [59]	Li-ion	66 kWh	9.3 hrs on 7.2 kW AC charge 1.25 hrs on 50 kW DC charge
Hyundai Ioniq Electric [60]	Li-ion Polymer	38.3 kWh	6 hrs on 7.2 kW AC charge 57 mins on 50 kW DC charge
Volkswagen e-Golf [61]	Li-ion	35.8 kWh	5.3 hrs on 7.2 kW AC charge 1 hr on 50 kW DC charge
Mercedes-Benz EQC [62]	Li-ion	80 kWh	11.5 hrs on 7.4 kW AC charge 40 mins on 110 kW DC charge
Kia e-Soul [63]	Li-ion Polymer	30.5 kWh	9.5 hrs on 7.2 kW AC charge 30 mins on 100 kW DC charge
Jaguar I-Place [64]	Li-ion	90 kWh	13 hrs on 7 kW AC charge 40 mins on 100 kW DC charge
Tesla S [65]	Li-ion	100 kWh	9 hrs on 10 kW AC charge 30 mins on 150 kW DC charge
Renault Zoe [66]	Li-ion	52 kWh	9.5 hrs on 7 kW AC charge 1 hr on 50 kW DC charge
Peugeot e-208 [67]	Li-ion	50 kWh	7.5 hrs on 7 kW AC charge 30 mins on 100 kW DC charge
Vauxhall Corsa-e [68]	Li-ion	50 kWh	7.5 hrs on 7.4 kW AC charge 30 mins on 100 kW DC charge

2.3 System Requirements

2.3.1 EV Battery

While ICE vehicles get energy from burning fossil fuel, an EV is powered from a battery. Unlike the batteries used in mobile phones, laptops and other battery-powered electronic devices, EV batteries are designed to achieve

prolonged running time with high power and energy capacity. Automakers have different EV passenger models, with battery capacities boasting up to 100 kWh. The study in [69] investigates larger battery capacities (200 kWh and above) for futuristic mobile usage and recommends subdividing the total battery unit into mechanically separated containers. When an EV is being charged, chemical reactions go one way and the battery absorbs power, these reactions are then reversed to produce electricity when the EV is being discharged. Some of the EV battery technologies widely deployed in the real world include lithium-ion (Li-ion), nickel-metal hydride (NiMH) and lead acid [70, 71]. Among them, Li-ion is the most common battery technology. Several potential technologies that might be able to achieve better or comparable performance to Li-ion batteries are in early stage of development. These include nickel-cadmium (NiCd), sodium-sulfur (NaS), zinc bromide (Zn-Br) and aluminium-air (Al-air) [72]. The study in [73] details the expected development in battery technology by 2030. As observed in Table 2.1, Li-ion is currently the widely accepted battery technology in the EV market [56–68]. This can be attributed to its lightweight, high density, low self-discharge rate and prolonged life features. The risk of explosion from overcharged cells and life cycle reduction from undercharged cells are the disadvantages associated with Li-ion batteries. The EV battery features in Table 2.1 are based on information published by the manufactures. The charging in AC considers the time from 0 to 100% charged, while the charging in DC considers the time from 10% to 80% charged or from 20% to 80% charged.

The lifespan of the Li-ion batteries are typically estimated through calendar life and cycle life. The calendar life is the retainable duration in terms of calendar years, independent of charge and discharge cycling [74]. The cycle life estimates the capacity retention during continuous charge and discharge cycling before degrading significantly [75]. To predict battery life, study its

behaviour and simulate its performance under dynamic conditions, a battery model is required. The types of battery models widely studied include electrochemical, experimental, mathematical and electric circuit models. The most accurate is the electrochemical models, however they require in-depth knowledge of the chemical reactions of batteries and complex set of equations that govern battery behaviour [76, 77]. Experimental models are based on experimentation to determine parameters associated with battery behaviour [78, 79]. Mathematical models consist of stochastic approaches that capture battery behaviour [80, 81]. Electric circuit models provide an equivalent representation of battery characteristics. The basic equivalent circuit model consists of an open-circuit voltage in series with a resistance and a parallel combination of resistance and capacitance [82–84].

2.3.2 EV Charging Station

An EV charging station, also called charge/charging point, electric recharging point and electric vehicle supply equipment (EVSE), is an equipment that connects an EV to the electricity grid. When EVs are plugged into a charge point, they can behave as loads or feed-back energy to the electricity grid. The rapid growth in the global EV market has led to the proliferation of charger designs, charging strategies, charging techniques and charging networks. Techniques for charging and discharging of EVs, with emphasis on convenience, simplicity, flexibility, and high efficiency, have become the motivation of current research in academic and industrial communities [85]. The two main charging solutions for EVs are conductive and inductive methods [86]. Conductive charging typically involves hard-wired connection (electrical contact) between EV and the source of electricity, or EV and load in a discharging scenario. While inductive charging works on the principle of inductive power transfer (IPT), where

TABLE 2.2: EV charging station characteristics and charging power levels in SAE J1772 standards [91, 92].

Parameters	Level 1	Level 2	Level 1	Level 2
Source	AC	AC	DC	DC
Typical Usage	Home or office base charging	Privately and publicly base charging	Dedicated charging stations	Dedicated charging stations
Interface for Energy Supply	Any convenient outlet	Electric Vehicle Supply Equipment	Electric Vehicle Supply Equipment	Electric Vehicle Supply Equipment
Power Capacity (kW)	1.9	19.2	350	350
Voltage (V)	120	240	200-1,000	200-1,000
Current (A)	16	80	500	500

magnetic field is used to transfer power across an air gap to a load. Here no power cable, physical contact or human intervention is required. The exclusion of cables, relatively low maintenance and autonomy for the driver has improved their practicality in V2G systems [87]. Although there have been recent progresses in inductive methods [88, 89], conductive methods remains the most common solution [90].

The time it takes to charge EV batteries is currently longer than the refuelling time of ICE vehicles to satisfy the same driving demands. EV charging rate is determined by how many kilowatts the charge point can provide and the EV can accept – the higher the power output, the faster the charge. Currently, the three main types of EV charging - representing the power outputs, and therefore charging speeds - are very slow, slow, and fast. Slow charging (level 1) can be done using existing electrical circuits. Level 1 chargers plug directly

into any convenient outlet, and are suitable for home or office use cases due to long charging sessions. Unlike the previous case, fast charging (level 2) requires installation of residential or public charging equipment. Level 2 chargers are largely deployed in public places such as park and ride facilities, shopping centres, car parks, airports and universities. While levels 1 and 2 charging are adequate to serve the day-to-day needs of EV owners, long-distance or unplanned trips in EVs need to be considered. Fast charging (level 3) is available in a much higher voltage using DC and can achieve 80% of charge in about 30 minutes, depending on the capacity of the EV [48]. Level 3 chargers are often used as range extenders along major roads and in urban environment to support drivers in urgent need. Level 3 DC charging is divided into two sub-categories: DC level 1 and DC level 2. It is to be noted that the charging types discussed here follow the Society of Automotive Engineers (SAE) J1722 standards and is used in regions such as North America, Japan and South Korea. EV charging station characteristics in SAE J1722 standards are presented in Table 2.2.

The International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) 61851 standards follow a similar structure to the SAE J1722 standards and is vastly used in regions such as the United Kingdom, Europe and Australia. The IEC 61851 standard defines four modes of charging. Mode 1 charging can be achieved with direct connection to a household socket outlet, using a standard cable and plug. Unlike the previous case, mode 2 charging requires the presence of a safety system for power control and protection between the EV and the household socket outlet. The safety system integrated into the connection cable is called a control box or in-cable control and protection device (IC-CPD). Mode 3 charging can be achieved through a specific equipment called EVSE, permanently connected to the electrical network. Control and protection functions are integrated in the installation. While charging in modes 1, 2 and 3 is

TABLE 2.3: EV charging station characteristics and charging power levels in IEC 61851 standards [91, 92].

Parameters	Mode 1	Mode 2	Mode 3	Mode 4
Source	AC	AC	AC	DC
Typical Usage	Home or office base charging	Privately and publicly base charging	Dedicated charging stations	Dedicated charging stations
Interface for Energy Supply	Convenient electrical outlet	Control box between EV and electrical outlet	Electric Vehicle Supply Equipment	Electric Vehicle Supply Equipment
Power Capacity (kW)	4 13.3	8 22	43	200
Voltage (V)	250, single phase 480, three phase	250, single phase 480, three phase	250, single phase 480, three phase	600
Current (A)	16	32	32-250	00

achieved by delivering AC to the EV on-board charger, mode 4 charging delivers DC directly to the EV battery, bypassing the on-board charger. EV charging station characteristics in IEC 61851 standards are presented in Table 2.3. A detailed study of the charging standards used globally is presented in [91, 92].

To achieve a refuelling time that is comparable to that of ICE vehicles, EVs would need charging stations with much higher power output. Extreme fast charging (XFC) is an emerging technology with potentials to address the fast charge barrier and be truly competitive to the ICE refuelling experience [93]. XFC stations should be able to support charging at 400 kW, recharge an EV in less than 10 minutes and provide up to 200 additional miles of driving [94]. However, there are still many barriers that need to be addressed towards the

standardisation and successful implementation of XFC. The technology gaps in XFC topology is identified in [95]. The study in [94] investigates the XFC technology-based charging infrastructure which will be necessary to support current and future EV refueling needs.

With EV batteries becoming cheaper, automakers are equipping new model EVs with more battery capacities. What used to be considered fast charging for a 24 kWh battery is no longer fast when the battery size reaches 60 kWh or more. To address the changing market environment and meet the expectations of EV stakeholders, CHAdeMO has developed an ultra-high-power charging protocol enabling 500 kW charging and allowing for maximum current of 600 A [96]. This new DC charging standard aims to support shorter and safer charging using ultra-fast charging technology and is another step closer to achieving a refueling time that can be competitive to the ICE refuelling experience. The background and technical challenges of harmonising this new DC charging standard and its impact on the global EV charging infrastructure outlook is presented in [97].

Different EV charging standards are adopted in different regions, with the main difference being the connector designs. For AC charging, regions such as North America and Japan adopted the SAE J1772 Type 1 connector (also known as J plug). It provides a maximum power of 19.2 kW (80 A at 240 V) [98]. The IEC 62196-2 Type 2 connector (often referred to as Mennekes in reference to the company that originated the design) is adopted in Europe for AC charging. Due to the drawable AC current limited to 32 A, the AC charging power is limited to 22 kW [99]. The GB/T 20234.2 connector is a modified IEC 62196-2 Type 2-style connector, adopted in China for AC charging. It uses connectors physically compatible with the IEC 62196-2 Type 2 connector, but with different control signalling. It allows AC charging at up to 27.7 kW (63 A at 440 V) [98].

For DC charging, China adopted the GB/T 20234.3 connector. It allows fast charging at a maximum of 237.5 kW, with current of 250 A and voltage of 950 V [100]. Combined charging system (CCS) or Combo connectors are used for DC fast charging. CCS connectors are extensions of the SAE J1772 Type 1 and IEC 62196-2 Type 2 connectors, with two additional DC pins at the bottom of the connectors for DC charging [91]. The CCS 1 (or Combo 1) connector is adopted in North America, while the CCS 2 (also known as IEC 62196-3 or Combo 2) connector is adopted in Europe. These connectors allow for fast charging at up to 350 kW [99]. While Japan uses the same connector (SAE J1772 Type 1) as North America for AC charging, it adopted the CHAdeMo connector for DC fast charging. This connector can withstand power of up to 400 kW [99]. Japan and China are developing an ultra-fast connector referred to as ChaoJi. This connector will be capable of charging up to 900 kW (at 600 A and 1,500 V) [99]. Tesla designed its own connector, which supports both AC and DC charging. The Tesla Supercharger connector supports fast charging at up to 500 kW and can connect to other connectors via specific adapter.

There is a growing interest in the integration of solar photovoltaic into the EV charging system. Solar-powered EV charging stations can help reduce GHG emissions, charging costs and the impact of additional load on the grid. Different technologies for solar-powered EV charging and their deployment in the real world are discussed in [101]. While solar-powered charging stations bring opportunities for EVs, the environment and the grid, the uncertainty and intermittent nature of solar power raises challenges in timely utilisation. The concentration of electricity output during the daytime limits the contribution of solar power in meeting a large fraction of typical energy demand. Thus, a grid connection or battery bank is necessary to guarantee effective operation of the solar-powered charging station.

2.3.3 Load

Load indicates an electrical component (device or machine) or a collection of equipment that consumes electrical energy. Based on demand response management, loads in a building can be divided into two categories: controllable and non-controllable. Non-essential loads that can be deferred or interrupted for a limited period of time with minimal effect on convenience are considered as controllable loads. These include air conditioners, water heaters, dish washers, clothes washers, clothes dryers and EVs. While loads such as lighting, cookers, microwave ovens and other plug loads are considered as non-controllable loads. Building loads in a power system can be categorised into two groups: critical and non-critical loads. Critical facilities which need to be operating during power outages such as hospitals, care homes, residential houses with life support equipment, water and communication infrastructure, control centres, data centres, evacuation centres, emergency shelters, police and fire stations, military bases and airports are considered as critical loads. Non-critical loads are not essential for human health and safety, and they would generally be loads not categorised under critical loads.

Load profile represents the pattern of energy usage of a consumer, both daily (on-peak and off-peak) and seasonally (summer and winter). Modern grids are usually known to be based on the behaviour of consumers to manage the load and supply in the distribution network, where reliable and efficient delivery of electric services are dependent on the load profile. Load forecasting is the predicting of power or energy needed to meet the short-term (up to a day), medium-term (a day up to a year) or long-term (over a year) demand. The load

profile can be forecasted using techniques such as similar-day approach, time-series method, regression method, neural networks, fuzzy logic, knowledge-based expert systems, adaptive load forecasting, iterative reweighted least-squares and exponential smoothing [102, 103]. The accuracy of forecasting is of significant importance for the planning and operation of electric utilities.

2.3.4 Advanced Metering Infrastructure

EVaaS applications require smart sensing systems which are able to get information in real-time on power consumption and power quality measurements to support energy management applications [104]. Advanced metering infrastructure (AMI), also known as smart metering, is an essential component in the realisation of the smart grid vision[105]. AMI is a configured infrastructure that integrates smart meters, data management systems and communication networks to enable two-way communication between the utility and consumer [106]. AMI provides time stamped information and establishes two-way communication between smart meter and the utility. With two-way communication, many services that were nearly impossible to implement without smart metering are now applicable. These services include power outage detection, power quality measurements and power flow monitoring [106]. The power flow monitoring information is important as it enables the utility to react rapidly on changes in consumption levels.

Unlike traditional meters, smart meters are self-reading meters which give more detailed information on energy usage in near-real time. The smart meter stores various types of data, such as executed or received commands, event logs, time of use tariffs and the firmware. The smart meter has either an Ethernet interface to connect to wireline services or a direct interface to a wireless

service. Data of the smart meter is collected and transmitted to the utility using wide area network (WAN) connection. Smart meter connections to home area network (HAN) are fundamental to residential or building management and allow appliances to respond to time-based pricing signals or other triggers carried over the grid. Key features of smart meters include load limiting and balancing for demand response applications, remote command (turn on/off) operations, power outage detection, time-based pricing, power quality monitoring (active and reactive power, phase, voltage, current and power factor) and power consumption measurement for utility and consumer.

2.4 EVaaS Communications

EVaaS communications enable data and information sharing among EVaaS subsystems, and it consists of communication infrastructure, such as wired and wireless networks, and processing facilities, such as data centre and cloud computing. The smart meter facilitates the transmission of data through commonly available fixed wired and wireless networks, such as Fixed Radio Frequency, Power Line Communication (PLC), Broadband over Power Line (BPL), as well as public networks such as cellular, landline and paging. Consumption data from the smart meters are received, stored and analyzed to provide useful insights to the utility. The smart meter also responds to remote command from the utility .

2.4.1 V2G Communications

V2G communications enable EVs and the grid to interact and exchange information. This is crucial to solve problems related to V2G management. By enabling real-time and reliable communication between EVs and the grid,

energy resources distributed over large geographical areas can be managed effectively to enhance the overall system performance. The communication network in V2G systems must be bidirectional to ensure substantial information exchange [107]. The system needs information control that is aware of EV location, battery capacity, battery efficiency, SOC, energy price and transportation cost. Transmitting this information and receiving commands over efficient bidirectional communication links is an essential requirement for successful V2G integration. Wireless communication is the ideal solution for V2G systems for various reasons, most notably because EVs are mobile and cannot connect to wireline services. Wireless communication enables the simultaneous transmission of data to dispersed EVs within a wide area coverage.

Different wireless communication technologies which have been implemented for short- and long-range data communication in V2G systems include Near Field Communication [108], Bluetooth [109], Zigbee [110], IEEE 802.11p [24] and WiMAX [111]. Bluetooth and ZigBee protocols are suitable for short-range data communication, such as between EV and charging station, offering a coverage area of up to 100m, while Near Field Communication suffers from very short communication range of up to 10cm [6]. IEEE 802.11p and WiMAX technologies are the standard protocols for long-range communications. The studies in [112, 113] details the IEEE 802.11p standard and mobile WiMAX (based on IEEE 802.16e standard). IEEE 802.11p technology, which offers a coverage area of up to 1km, data rates of up to 54 Mbps and latency as low as 50 ms, is the popular standard for vehicular networks. WiMAX technology, on the other hand, has similar features as IEEE 802.11p but offers longer range communication of up to 5km, higher data transfer speed of up to 100 Mbps and very low delays between 25-40 ms.

Recent studies have investigated the use of wireless communications in V2G environments. The study in [20] details the communication requirements to

gather data from various entities such as EVs and the grid and other grid resources as well as to communicate with EVs for control purposes. The technologies, protocols and block components needed for enabling IP communications in mobile V2G environments are discussed in [21]. A smart charging system which acquires EV data and transmits control instructions to the charging station via GPRS and ZigBee is proposed in [22]. The study in [24] presents two IEEE 802.11p-based quality of service schemes that enable the interaction between EVs and the grid for coordinated EV charging. The study in [25] modeled the average delay time for a group of charging EVs based on Markov chain representation for the wireless IEEE 802.11 MAC protocol, which considers the impact of a lossy wireless link between EVs and the access point. The study in [26] proposed an EV charging management scheme utilizing vehicular communication between EVs and access points based on IEEE 1609 WAVE and IEC 61850 standards. A software-defined networking-based control scheme for vehicular communication networks is developed in [27]. An EV charging scheduling scheme which considers the impact of data communication unavailability on the charging station scheduling performance is developed in [23]. A joint optimisation model of energy cost and radio usage for discharging EVs in V2G communication networks is proposed in [114].

For successful V2G integration, communication is required between EV and EVSE to control the charging and discharging process. An EVSE enables EVs with different charging and communication requirements to connect to the load or supply network. Digital communication between EV and EVSE is essential to initiate or terminate energy transfer to and from EVs. This has facilitated the creation of several standards to regulate the EV-EVSE interface and the communications requirements. In the IEC 61851, International Organization for Standardization (ISO) 15118-2 and SAE J2847-2 standards, PLC has been adopted for communications between EV and EVSE [115–117]. While in the

GB/T 27930-2015 and CHAdeMo standards, communication between EV and EVSE is realised on Controller Area Network (CAN) bus [96, 118]. The communication network that enable data exchange in EV-EVSE environments is shown in Figure 2.2.

FIGURE 2.2: Communication network in EV-EVSE environment.

2.4.2 Data Analytics

The performance of the UK's internet-based 4G cellular network for V2G energy trading market applications is evaluated in [119]. Sample data sizes from 50B to 2KB are used to imitate different scenarios. The study considered a scenario where a single aggregator serves a parking lot, and the latency performance was marginally better than the UK market threshold. The study highlighted the need to use low latency 5G networks for more complicated scenarios such as multiple aggregators to multiple parking lots and physically distant EVs. However, due to lack of 5G city-wide coverage, the analysis was left as future work. 5G network aims to support the deployment of vehicles-to-everything (V2X) technologies, cater to explosive ever-growing data traffic and enable users to indulge in gigabit speed immersive services capable of extremely low response time, regardless of geographical and time dependent factors [120]. V2X technology will facilitate autonomous energy trading, where EVs in parking lots can autonomously charge and discharge their batteries,

while self-driving EVs can be routed to appropriate charging stations to participate in EVaaS activities. EVaaS requires much shorter network response time and big data analytics to enable rapid reactions and intelligence across the network. There is no doubt that large amounts of data will be generated by sensors, smart meters, cameras, maps, on-board electronic control unit and battery management system of EVs, databases and more.

EV data which can be used to monitor, analyse and make decisions relating to charging/discharging, energy trading and range estimation mostly come from the on-board electronic control units and battery management system. EV data can be categorised as into three types, namely standard, historical and real-time data. Standard data include technical specifications from manufacturer and the usual driving time to destination according to Google Map. Historical data include battery management system logs showing start and end times of journeys, as well as SOC information like connect and disconnect times of charges and discharges. Real-time data include SOC of EV battery, GPS location of EV and data closely related to emergency issues, such as unplanned road closures and real-time traffic/weather condition. Internet of things (IoT) enables the recording and transmitting of detailed EV data in on-board computers or cloud computing infrastructure. In the context of the smart grid, IoT is built by integrating internet-connectivity into all grid subsystems, connecting them in intelligent networks, and utilizing data analytics to extract meaningful and actionable insights from them [121]. Cloud computing provides the virtual infrastructure for data collection, analysis and visualisation in the current architecture of IoT.

During mobility, autonomous EVs can generate data up to thousands of gigabytes, where the volume of data is dependent on the variety of sensors and cameras used for autonomy. Data generation is not expected to be enormous during EVaaS, but the various sensors collecting data from grid, EVs, smart

meters, charging stations and drivers will need solutions from the big data domain. Effective integration of data from different sources is possibly an enormous task; however, with the right tools and solutions from the big data domain, valuable insights can be drawn [122]. Prioritizing the intercepted information is essential and means of prioritisation should be investigated, as decision-makers can only digest a certain amount of information and draw insights based on it. Furthermore, the processing of EV data by the aggregator make EVs vulnerable to security and privacy concerns, which are yet to be addressed in the domain of big data analytics for EVs.

2.5 Charging Strategies

Large-scale deployment of EVs will result in higher demands on distribution systems, which were not originally designed to withstand a high level of EV penetration [123]. With the expected rise in penetration levels, future EV charging scenarios could be accompanied by numerous challenges. EV charging profile has an effect on the distribution system. The increasing number of charging EVs adds extra load on distribution systems, which can drastically impact electricity grid stability. These impacts include power quality issues, phase imbalance, transformer degradation and failure, higher system losses and increased operational cost [124]. We review different charging strategies and their impact on distribution systems. This review classifies the EV charging strategies into uncoordinated and coordinated strategies.

2.5.1 Uncoordinated Charging

Uncoordinated charging describes a scenario where the EV batteries either start charging immediately EVs are plugged into a charge point or after a

user-adjustable fixed delay, and continues charging until the batteries are completely charged or unplugged. In uncoordinated charging, EV charging is presumably at Level 1 (Modes 1 and 2) with no coordinative control action. Thus, its impact on distribution systems is primarily driven by the stochastic behaviour of the EV user [125]. Load at peak hours tend to increase with uncoordinated charging operations. An increase in peak load can cause severe network stress and overloads in the local distribution grid. Random uncoordinated charging may lead to increased power losses, overloads in transformer and cables, poor voltage profiles, degraded power quality and an overall reduction in the reliability and economy of the distribution grid [126].

An analysis into the impacts of random uncoordinated EV charging on the performance of distribution transformers was carried out in [127]. Results revealed that even under low EV penetrations, transformer load surging and voltage deviations were significant. Load growth on transformers for low penetration level of 17% to 31% showed a 37% to 74% increase in transformer load current. In [128], a test model using household load profiles for Belgium reports voltage deviations close to 10% during evening peak for a penetration level of 30%. A typical UK distribution system is studied in [129] to determine the impact of uncontrolled domestic charging on the distribution system. Results show up to 17.9% increase in daily peak demand at 10% penetration rate of EVs, while the peak load would increase by 35.8% at 20% EV penetration. In [123], the impact of EV penetration on existing electricity distribution infrastructure was analysed using data for the Netherlands. Results show that at 30% EV penetration, uncoordinated charging would increase national peak load and household peak load by 7% and 54%, respectively, which may exceed the capacity of the distribution system. The utility operator will have to increase peak generation if the load exceeds peak capacity. The cost of additional generation capacity during peak period is then passed on to EV

owners. In [130], uncontrolled charging was shown to cause a 22% increase in the monthly energy bill, even at just 10% EV penetration.

Some energy suppliers in the UK offer EV tariffs to help reduce peak demand, redirecting it to off-peak times [131]. The two-rate tariff, which offers cheaper rates during off-peak times (overnight), is designed to encourage EV owners to charge when the energy demand is low, and generation is mostly base load. The study in [129] showed that overnight charging increases off-peak energy consumption but it had no impact on the daily peak load. In [123], off-peak charging at 30% penetration rate of EVs was reported to cause a 20% higher, more stable base load and no additional peak load on the national grid. Thus, with the introduction of off-peak charging, additional generation capacity would not be required for low EV penetrations.

2.5.2 Coordinated Charging

Coordinated charging is being investigated as an alternative and possible solution to random uncoordinated charging and its associated problems, respectively. EV charging is most likely at Levels 2 and 3 in coordinated charging [47]. By utilizing the control and bidirectional communications infrastructure of smart grids, smart coordinated charging and discharging of EVs can reduce transformer load surges, line currents, voltage deviations and daily energy costs [126, 128, 132]. It can also provide efficient energy usage [129] and flatten the voltage profile of a distribution node [133]. Incremental distribution network investment and energy losses costs can be avoided with the implementation of smart charging strategies. Results in [134] showed the possibility of avoiding up to 60%-70% of the required incremental investment with smart

charging. The results of the study in [135] reveal that coordinated charging of EVs minimises system losses and improves voltage regulation in the distribution grid.

Smart charging and discharging where EVs charge their batteries from RESs and discharge them during peak demand is reported to offer the best possible utilisation of RESs for cost and emission reductions in the smart grid [16, 136, 137]. It can improve operational performance in stand-alone operation mode and increase the quantity of RESs installed in islanded microgrids [132]. A control strategy was implemented in [138] to coordinate the charging and discharging of EVs to support a grid with high penetration of wind energy. The obtained results showed that the total power imbalance in the system was significantly suppressed. In [139], coordinated EV charging and discharging was implemented on an Australian distribution grid with solar power generation. The proposed control method was able to cope with solar power uncertainty and efficient in improving grid performance, reducing energy cost and mitigating grid imbalance.

Coordinated charging can be categorised into two types, namely centralised and decentralised approaches. In centralised approaches, EV charging is directly controlled by a centralised unit (microgrid control centre or aggregator). Centralised approaches offer full support for ancillary services. However, only a limited number of charging EVs can be accommodated. Another drawback of this approach is that it involves higher order complexity. In decentralised approaches, the power of decision-making with regards to EV charging is distributed among individual EVs. The charging behaviour of EVs can be directly influenced by a price signal. Decentralised approaches offer greater scalability and lesser computational complexity. Considering EVs only have to exchange limited information with the aggregator, their privacy is preserved [140]. A drawback in this approach is the need for EVs to collect and store the

trip history [141]. Compared with centralised approaches, the decentralised approaches are more scalable, flexible, and enables EV owners to partake in the decision-making process of EV charging.

2.6 Energy Trading and Market Design

Advances in V2G promises unprecedented improvements in operational efficiency. This unlocks the possibility of prosumer and consumer participation in energy trading. Consumers equipped with rooftop solar power system can emerge as EV-prosumers and self-supply during peak period or power outages using V2H integration [142]. This can lead to reduced household energy costs, maximum utilisation of solar power generation and minimum dependency of domestic loads on the grid. In an EVaaS energy trading scenario, a grid manager (aggregator) has a demand target and manages individual or aggregated EVs to fulfill the demand. Energy trading can be categorised according to the market design. We review two types of energy trading in V2G environments: traditional bilateral energy trading used in conventional energy industry and futuristic energy trading with increased distributed influence, based on blockchain technology.

2.6.1 Traditional Energy Trading

Traditional energy industry has operated on a centralised energy trading model for decades. In centralised approaches, one user or a centralised controller dictates to a group of users, while acting collectively as one entity. The central controller, acting as an energy broker, is assumed to know all the information about trading entities and tries to match demand and supply. The

appropriate framework to employ in a centralised market would be single objective optimisation models such as swarm, stochastic or convex optimisation, or social welfare maximisation [143]. Decentralised energy markets enables scalability and competitiveness amongst self-interested EVs compared to their centralised counterparts. Thus, it is important to investigate distributed economic approaches which incentivizes energy trading between EVs and the grid [144].

Auction is a promising market mechanism used to sell (forward auction) or buy (reverse auction) energy in smart grids, with the aggregator acting as auctioneer. In a scenario where energy trade is incentivized, buyers pay a discount in forward auction while sellers receive a premium in reverse auction as compared to the clearing price. The amount of energy to be traded and the final price to be paid is the outcome of the auction. Based on the final payment, there are different auctions schemes, namely first price auction, second price auction and uniform price auction [145]. Utility-maximising bidders could misrepresent their valuations (individually or collusively) by not bidding truthfully, which could harm the fairness and efficiency of the trade. Vickrey-Clarke-Groves (VCG) auction is effective in ensuring the properties of truthfulness [146–148]. An auction scheme that enables EVs and batteries in swap stations to trade energy is proposed in [149]. A double auction-based approach for enabling EVs to trade their excess energy to the grid is studied in [150]. Double auction mechanism has also been studied in [13, 151] for energy trading in a two-layer V2G architecture, made up of grid-aggregator and aggregator-EV layers. In [12], a group-selling strategy for V2G demand response management is implemented through a two-layer reverse auction.

Game-theoretic approach is another promising solution which has been used in numerous applications to study the interactions among self-interested and independent agents. A game is made up of three essential elements: a set of

players, a set of actions (strategies) and a set of payoffs (utility functions). The payoff obtained by the players is the value of the game. One major strategy for game theory is the Nash equilibrium, where no player has any incentive by unilaterally deviating from its strategy. Based on players coordinating or competing with themselves, games can be categorised into two types, namely cooperative games and noncooperative games. Noncooperative games are appropriate in distributed energy trading scenarios between competitive trading entities. While cooperative games are ideal in scenarios where trading entities cooperate with the aid of communication networks, in order to optimise the efficiency or social welfare of the collaborators. In [152], an analytical framework that captures the interactions between a smart grid and EV groups is modelled using a noncooperative Stackelberg game. The interactions and energy trading decisions of physically distant storage units, such as EVs, is studied in [153] using a noncooperative game. An incentive-based V2V game theoretic approach that captures the coordination strategies of EVs and battery swapping station aggregators is modelled in [154]. In order to incentivize EV participation, each battery swapping station aggregator implements a noncooperative game among the EVs in its range through a smart pricing scheme. Collaborative and non-collaborative approaches which considers energy trading and residential load scheduling with EVs is proposed in [155]. The collaborative approach is based on social welfare maximisation, while the non-collaborative approach utilises a noncooperative game. Besides auction and game theory, incentive-based approaches such as pricing, bargain and contract theories, which are able to study the interaction between self-interested participants and improve the efficiency of energy trade, have been widely deployed [144].

2.6.2 Blockchain-Based Energy Trading

With the rising penetration of EVs, satisfying the ever-increasing energy demand of V2G applications remains a challenge for the distribution system. To address this challenge, recent studies have exploited blockchain technology for energy trading in V2G environments. Blockchain technology enables increased distributed influence in the distribution system, while preserving privacy and maintaining transparency and system security [156]. This will improve the flexibility of the conventional energy market, enable a consumer-centric energy market and support prosumer participation. EVs, acting as prosumers or consumers, will be able to trade energy in a peer-to-peer (P2P) manner without third-party intervention as shown in Figure 2.3.

FIGURE 2.3: Types of energy trading in V2G environments.

The application of blockchain technology for EV-enabled energy trading in smart grids is briefly discussed in [157]. A decentralised security model based

on the lightning network and smart contracts is proposed in [158] to protect energy trading transactions between EVs and charging stations. A localised P2P energy trading model based on consortium blockchain is proposed in [159]. The model uses iterative double auction mechanism to maximise social welfare of charging and discharging EVs. Consortium blockchain has also been exploited in [160] to propose an energy trading model applicable in general scenarios of P2P energy trading. The model uses Stackelberg game to maximise economic benefits. A private blockchain was applied in [161] to establish a trusted environment for energy trading between EVs and critical loads and a prototype was developed for remotely monitoring of energy trading activities.

While P2P energy trading is promising, one of its major impediments is regulation. Currently, decentralised energy trading is prohibited by regulation in the UK and some other EU countries, however this could change in the future. Business owners or individuals who generate electricity are limited to use it on site or sell directly to the utility grid for a nominal price. This poses a major barrier to P2P energy trading which enables direct trade between prosumers and consumers, instead of selling to and buying from the utility grid, respectively. Ideally, the authorisation of P2P energy trading will create a competitive energy market, allow prosumers generate revenue on their excess energy and consumers obtain cost effective energy. It is expected that energy prices will drop as a result of eliminating the middle man and more individuals incentivized to partake in microgeneration.

2.7 Benefits of V2G

2.7.1 Ancillary Services

V2G systems facilitates and encourages EVs participation in V2G, where EVs offer various ancillary services to the electric power grid. Ancillary services are essential for balancing demand and supply, maintaining grid reliability and supporting power transmission.

2.7.1.1 Reserve Power Supply

V2G systems can maintain the balance between demand and supply in electricity grids by injecting power. While the supply capacity for individual EV is small, an aggregated capacity can be significant to provide value to the grid. Aggregators are expected to collect EVs into a group to create a larger, more manageable capacity for the utility. For example, by simultaneously discharging their batteries, aggregated EVs will be able to provide additional power required by commercial building during peak demand, acting like a spinning reserve in the existing distribution system.

2.7.1.2 Voltage and Frequency Regulation

V2G systems are capable of regulating voltage and frequency in electricity grids. Frequency regulation provides active power support in the electricity grid. The exact amount of electricity being used needs to be matched by generation, if there is an imbalance it can affect the frequency of the electricity grid. For example, if electricity demand is more than supply, frequency will fall. If there is too much power being generated in relation to demand, frequency will rise. The frequency will not stabilise until the system is balanced.

In the UK, anything just 1% above or below the nominal frequency of 50Hz risks damaging electrical equipment and infrastructure, including appliances of end users [162]. Currently, frequency regulation is achieved mainly by turning on fast-responding generators to increase power generation, which is costly. Alternatively, fast charging and discharging rates of EV batteries can help to increase the load demand and generation, respectively. This makes V2G a promising alternative for frequency regulation [163, 164]. Voltage regulation provides reactive power support in the electricity grid. Reactive power can be controlled by selecting the current phase angle to provide inductive or capacitive action. The consumption of reactive power is mostly through inductive load, which requires the addition of capacitive reactive power to balance the demand. Traditionally, reactive power support is injected at the transmission or distribution grid stage, with no involvements from the end-users. However, with increased EV penetration, V2G can provide the necessary reactive power support to the grid. This is achieved through a DC to AC converter system usually embedded within the EV charger.

2.7.1.3 Peak Shaving and Load Levelling

V2G systems are capable of levelling peak loads in electricity grids. Peak load shaving is achieved through a control strategy that manages EV charging and discharging. In this technique, controllable and aggregated EVs can charge when demand is low (off-peak hours or overnight) and discharge during high demand (peak hours). In scenarios where the generation capacity does not match the peak demand, several problems such as voltage fluctuation, instability and total blackout could possibly occur. Therefore, by shaving peak load, the reliability and stability of the grid is maintained and supply shortage is mitigated. Previous studies had proposed different peak shaving and

valley filling techniques through V2G to alleviate the generation-demand imbalance [135, 165, 166]. This function of V2G can provide economic benefits as it limits the need to use high-priced peak generators.

2.7.2 Mobile Backup Power Supply

V2G systems are capable of restoring supply during prolonged grid outages and can improve the grid capabilities to withstand unexpected contingencies. Power systems must not only operate reliably in response to foreseeable contingencies, but also resilient to high-impact low-probability events [4]. Keeping critical loads operating during prolonged grid outages is a key resilience feature for mitigating its consequences [167]. Thus, following an unexpected system failure, fast recovery is very essential to enhance grid resilience. EVs, as mobile storage resources, can distribute the existing energy produced or stored in the local region. Aggregated EVs will be able to provide backup power required by critical loads during a blackout. In a scenario where the distribution network is partly damaged during an extreme event and regular supply cannot reach critical loads, EVs can be deployed to individual locations of the critical load to restore supply [161].

2.7.3 Renewable Energy Supporting and Balancing

V2G systems can support intermittent renewable energy in electricity grids. Due to the intermittent nature of wind and solar plants, their large-scale integration into the current electricity grid would require a large-capacity scale storage system [168–170]. In the UK for instance, peak solar radiation precedes peak demand by a few hours – solar peak power is at noon, peak demand is typically between mid-afternoons to late afternoons. On the other hand,

the stochastic nature of wind power is due to unpredictable variations in wind speed. Wind generation fluctuates and cannot be turned up when energy demand increases, leading to imbalances. At low scale penetration, existing mechanisms for managing supply and demand fluctuations can handle the intermittency of renewable energy. However, at high levels of penetration, additional resources are needed to match the fluctuating supply to the already fluctuating demand. If there is too much energy being generated from renewable sources, generation from conventional power plants must be curtailed to restore balance. EVs can help match generation and consumption by charging and discharging so the utility does not consider decreasing the power output. Thus, V2G increases the flexibility of the grid to support intermittent renewables.

2.7.4 Environmental Benefits

V2G systems can offer societal benefits regarding climate change, GHG emissions and air pollution. Climate change benefits come about via controlled charging (or peak shaving) to limit usage of high carbon energy sources, decarbonisation of the ancillary service market and electrification of the transport sector. The carbon benefits of V2G are mostly dependent on the electricity generation mix of the grid. In electricity grids with high polluting sources, V2G providing ancillary services has potentials to increase total carbon emissions [171]. EVs cannot guarantee decarbonisation since they are not generation. If EVs charge their batteries from a grid with high penetration of coal in its generation mix, their environmental advantages are more limited. However, if EVs are powered by cleaner energy sources, they can help reduce GHG emissions [172, 173]. From a transportation perspective, EV penetration possess potentials to reduce air pollution compared to ICE vehicles [174].

Direct emissions from ICE vehicle activity has an effect on public health, agriculture and natural environment. Thus, high penetration of EVs diminishes health and environmental costs.

2.7.5 Economic Benefits

V2G systems can offer economic benefits to EV owners, the power system and energy service providers. By applying peak shaving and valley filling techniques through coordinated EV charging and discharging, V2G can help reduce the capital cost needed to reinforce the network. By regulating frequency in electricity grids using EVs instead of expensive generators, V2G can help reduce the need to curtail cheap renewable output. As participants in V2G services would be incentivized, V2G provides the opportunity for EV owners to benefit from an additional revenue stream. The study in [175] provides insight into the financial returns available to EV stakeholders using V2G. Through stacking of different revenue streams such as day-ahead power market trading, third party cost component avoidance and Firm Frequency Response (FFR), the analysis estimates that V2G services could generate annual financial benefits ranging between £700 to £1250 per participating EV. Analysis also showed that each participating EV could reduce annual system operation costs by around £12,000. The study in [50] discussed the added economic value which can be accessed by using V2G. It also highlighted that the scale of this value is extremely variable and subject to a range of factors relating to EV charger usage and EV user behaviour. By assessing different EV user archetypes, and revenue streams such as FFR, imbalance management, energy price arbitrage, Short Term Operating Reserve (STOR) and Demand Turn Up (DTU), the analysis estimates that V2G services could achieve annual revenues of around £436. The study in [51] show that from revenue

streams such as offering flexibility to central markets via an aggregator and optimisation against a Time of Use (ToU) tariff, V2G could make around £410 annually.

2.8 Challenges to V2G

2.8.1 Battery Degradation

Despite the many benefits V2G offers, a major concern has been its impact on the degradation of EV batteries. V2G operation imposes more use (and stress) on EV batteries compared to daily driving, which likely accelerates the aging of EV batteries [176]. This can be associated with the increase in charge cycle, where a charge cycle is a complete charge and discharge process on the battery. EV battery usage is limited to a fixed number of cycles, over time the capacity (amount of energy that can be stored or extracted from the battery) degenerates significantly. Determination of V2G impact on EV battery degradation is still at the research stage with recent studies arriving at contradictory conclusions [177–180]. While some studies found EV battery degradation costs to be a substantial barrier to V2G [177, 178], others found the effect of EV battery degradation to be minimal [179, 180]. Nevertheless, even in the best-case scenario, participation in V2G operation accelerates battery capacity degradation beyond what is required to satisfy the driving demands [181]. Consequently, EVs may be expected to undergo battery replacement multiple times over their service life. Thus, V2G influences the frequency of battery replacement and associated costs.

2.8.2 Energy Conversion Losses

In V2G systems, energy losses occur between the grid connection point and the EV battery. Each time EVs are charged or discharged, energy losses occur in the EV and its supporting electrical infrastructure such as charging station, breakers and transformer. Each stage of storage, conversion and transmission contribute to the losses. This is considering the efficiencies of system components such as EV battery, power electronic unit, charging station, breaker panel and transformer. A comparison of empirical and assumed round-trip efficiency from different V2G economic analyses is presented in [182]. Although the studies in [182] have reported round-trip losses for EVs and related V2G infrastructure, efficiency values are case dependent and will differ among EVs and electrical circuits. Nevertheless, they can serve as a reference point for future studies on economic analysis of V2G.

2.8.3 Effects on Distribution System

The increasing penetration of EVs is likely to have considerable impact on the distribution system. Since the distribution grid is still focused on conventional design and operational rules, service capabilities of V2G devices tend to be limited. The charging and discharging of EVs introduces a change in the overall load profile of the distribution system. Uncontrolled EV charging adds to the pre-existing peak load, especially during fast charging. The load demand is centralised at the fast charging station and fast charging mainly occurs during the daytime, allowing EVs draw high power larger than a regular household load [183]. The interconnection of fast charging stations with the grid might create negative impacts on the distribution system [184]. Fast charging of EVs could result in detrimental effects on distribution transformers, lower operational efficiency of the distribution network equipment and rise

in energy losses. Fast charging also has adverse effects on the voltage profile and power quality of the network. Additional EV load increases transformer temperatures, which contributes to insulation breakdown and may decrease the life expectancy of the transformer [185]. The impact of different penetrations of EVs on a residential distribution transformer was studied in [186]. This revealed that high penetration of EVs can have significant impact on the electricity grid, particularly in scenarios with uncoordinated charging. In order to help the distribution network to accommodate EV penetration, a demand response strategy is proposed in the context of a smart distribution network in [187]. Thus, the effect of V2G on the distribution network is greatly influenced by the charging strategies and vehicle aggregation [188].

2.8.3.1 Power Quality

Power quality problems created by EVs, and EV charging infrastructure pose a significant challenge for the distribution system. Highly varying EV charging characteristics have negative effects on the distribution network [189]. In [190], an investigation was carried out to evaluate some of the effects of EV deployment on existing distribution networks. This revealed that high deployment of EVs may lead to power quality problems. EV charging infrastructure are known to affect the distribution network; thus, contributing to power quality degradation [191]. Non-linear loads, such as EV chargers, often introduce power quality problems within distribution networks, which increase losses in electrical equipment and power distribution [192]. Due to the power electronic components used in EV chargers, high deployment of EVs increases the risk of power quality problems [193]. The study in [194] revealed that the severity of impact on power quality is dependent on EV charger characteristics and robustness of the V2G network. In urban areas, depending on the load per area, increased demand due to EV charging may repeatedly overload distribution

transformers and adversely impact their operational life. While unplanned additional EV load can cause under-voltage problems in rural areas.

2.8.3.2 Harmonic Distortion

While coordinated EV charging and discharging improves grid performance, it can backfire if maintained sporadically. EVs can be charged using single-phase or three-phase connections. Most UK homes are connected to a single-phase supply, and majority of EV charging is expected to be done at home with single-phase chargers [195]. If any single phase of the three-phase system is overloaded explicitly due to uncoordinated domestic EV charging, it could create an unbalanced three-phase system, altering voltage and current flow, and system harmonics. The study in [196] revealed that EV charging can contaminate the distribution system with high amount of harmonic injection. Additionally, current harmonic emissions are produced by EV chargers, which in turn causes voltage harmonics [197]. The impact of EV charger harmonics on the distribution network was analysed in [193], with recent studies arriving at contradictory conclusions. High levels of harmonic distortion can cause several disturbances and damages, including decreasing the life cycle of distribution network equipment.

2.8.3.3 Voltage Unbalance

Voltage unbalance is majorly caused by the uneven distribution of single-phase loads, that may change frequently across a three-phase distribution system [198]. Voltage unbalance can result in adverse effects on equipment, such as power electronic converters, variable speed drives and induction motors. Under unbalanced conditions, the equipment will would experience excessive heating, reduced efficiency, increased losses and reduction in life cycle [198].

A large aggregation of EVs may cause voltage imbalance in a three-phase distribution system. Voltage unbalance problems can occur when heavy unequal single-phase EV load are connecting and disconnecting into the distribution system at different time interval [199]. The study in [190] showed that, under certain operating conditions, high EV deployment could lead to voltage imbalance in a three-phase system. The study in [199] revealed that voltage imbalance will increase as a result of increased level of EV penetration. The impact of voltage imbalance was shown to be greater when EVs are connected to the end of the feeder.

2.9 Summary

In this chapter, the EVaaS framework where suitable EVs are selected to provide grid-related services, individually or as part of an aggregation, was introduced. The EVaaS system architecture and interactions among EVaaS subsystems such as EV battery, charging station, load and communication infrastructure have been discussed. A methodology to enhance grid resilience through building-load categorisation was introduced. The centralised structure of conventional energy markets does not allow the full potential of V2G to be realised. The current energy market is not consumer-centric and does not support prosumer participation. Policy change, supporting infrastructure and incentives would play a huge role in maximising the market opportunities presented by V2G. Based on the EVaaS framework, the deployment of discharging EVs in the distribution network is investigated in later chapters from three aspects: economic, emissions and communications. The next chapter investigates EV deployment from the economic perspective of the EV owners.

Chapter 3

VCG-Based Auction for Incentivized Energy Trading

3.1 Introduction

Based on the electric vehicle as a service (EVaaS) framework introduced in chapter 2, the deployment of discharging EVs in the distribution network is investigated from the economic perspective of the EV owners. This chapter introduces an incentivized energy trading approach to study the interaction between electric vehicles (EVs) and critical load (CL) in a one-sided energy market. It addresses the second and third research questions of this thesis. Traditionally, EVs are managed under a centralised system where the grid manager is assumed to have full information and control over participating EVs. However, these approaches are not scalable considering the large number of physically distant EVs, and impractical due to the unwillingness of EV owners to share their private information. Hence, it is important to investigate distributed approaches which enable scalability and consider the interests of

EV owners. Incentivizing energy trading in distributed EV-enabled microgrids is both desirable and challenging.

3.1.1 Background

To address this challenge, economic incentive approaches are often applied to depict the behaviour of trading entities [144]. Here, trading entities are motivated to participate in the market via monetary incentives [200]. Auction is a promising mechanism used to capture the interactions between sellers and buyers in decentralised markets [145]. Auctions can be categorised according to the market design. Auctions in which at least one side of the the market consists of a single buyer or seller are single auctions, while two-sided markets in which multiple sellers and buyers may be making bids and offers simultaneously are called double auctions. It is generally assumed that bidders voluntarily represent their true valuation. However, bidders could misrepresent their valuations in order to maximise their utility. Vickrey-Clarke-Groves (VCG) mechanism is effective in ensuring the properties of incentive compatibility [201]. In VCG mechanism, bidding truthfully is a weakly dominant strategy, so there is no incentive for bidders to misrepresent their valuations.

Several recent works have applied VCG mechanism to a wide range of EV-enabled energy trading applications. In [8], EVs are incentivized to trade charging/discharging energy in active distribution systems and VCG-based pricing rule is applied to determine the payments EVs should make/receive. Double auction models are considered in [9] where autonomous EVs are incentivized to participate in dynamic energy trading with energy aggregators and two incentive payment schemes are proposed. Multiple buyers and multiple sellers are involved in the auctioning process in these works; therefore, it is not inapplicable in a one-sided market. In [10], two extensions of second

price auction mechanisms were applied and studied for EV charging control in smart grids, where EVs are required to declare limited valuation to the auctioneer. This poses implementation difficulties in a market environment that requires entire valuation declaration.

In [11], an online continuous progressive second price-based auction scheme is proposed for EV charging in fast charging reservation systems. In [12], an auction mechanism for Vehicle-to-grid (V2G) systems is proposed and a feedback-based price scheme is designed to incentivize EV participation. An auction mechanism is designed in [13] to stimulate EV discharging in V2G systems. In [14], an auction mechanism is proposed to jointly incentivize discharging EVs and utilise local generation to charge EVs during emergency demand response periods. The incentives from these auction mechanisms may not cover battery degradation incurred during energy trading; hence, EV owners may incur revenue loss if they are not compensated. An auction-based scheme which enables local energy trading among EVs and considers battery wear-out cost is proposed in [15]. A battery degradation model is also presented to depict a practical energy trading environment. However, the scheme employs a naive auction process which does not examine essential economic properties such as truthfulness and individual rationality. The auction models in the literature do not consider EV mobility. Ideally, EVs are distributed over the local region and would need to travel from one location to another to supply energy [161].

3.1.2 Our Contributions

In this chapter, we introduce an incentivized energy trading approach, where EVs distributed within the microgrid are chosen to balance demand-supply mismatch. In the proposed approach, EVs enforce their conditions to participate in the bidding process such as the minimum and maximum amount of

energy they are willing to sell. This ensures EVs are not subjected to unfair trade conditions where winning bidders sell an undesirable amount of energy as it is with centralised systems and protects the battery from deep discharge. The major contributions of this chapter are as follows.

- We formulate the EV-CL association problem as a single auction and the discharging scheduling optimisation problem for EVs distributed within the microgrid. The auction determines the winning bids and the corresponding payments, while the discharging scheduling determines the discharging power of associated EVs for all time intervals.
- A number of practical constraints such as energy demand, power balance, state of charge (SoC) and charging station limits are captured in the problem formulation. The approach integrates battery degradation and transportation costs to ensure EV owners are compensated for battery degradation incurred during EV-CL interaction. We utilise a similar-day approach load forecasting model to estimate the CL demand.
- The proposed energy trading model is evaluated in comparative studies with centralised and exiting schemes. Numerical results demonstrate that the model guarantees bidder satisfaction, as well as the economic properties of truthfulness and individual rationality.

3.2 System Model

3.2.1 System Description

Electric vehicle as a service (EVaaS) describes a system where suitable EVs in the microgrid are chosen to exchange energy with CL [54]. The energy trading

FIGURE 3.1: One-sided energy market with EVs and CL in a microgrid.

process between EVs and CL is modeled using a one-sided auction with the aggregator acting as an auctioneer, as shown in Figure 3.1. The aggregator coordinates the auction between EVs and CL through dedicated communication networks. V2G communication networks support bidirectional information exchange [114], which allows EVs to participate in the bidding process from anywhere within the microgrid. However, various factors such as distance between EV and CL, transportation cost and required energy for transportation (to CL and back) need to be considered. Charging stations are utilised as sources for EVs to exchange energy with CL. The proposed approach assumes that the discharging rate of EVs are fixed and energy transfer losses in the charging stations are not considered.

3.2.2 Battery Degradation Model

EV battery degradation creates a common concern for EV owners when considering EVaaS participation. Due to natural limitations, the EV battery has a limited amount of charge cycles, where a charge cycle is a complete charge

and discharge process. At the end of the estimated number of charge cycles specified by the manufacturer, the battery will start losing capacity and its performance will decrease significantly [75]. Increased charge cycles due to EVaaS participation would accelerate the battery degradation, resulting in revenue loss to the EV owner. The capacity loss and high cost of battery sum up the major financial liabilities of the EV owners and a compensation is required for the losses incurred [202].

We consider a linear battery model which assumes the number of charge cycles multiplied by the depth of discharge (DoD) corresponds to 1 cycle of 100% DoD, i.e., 5 cycles of 20% DoD as equivalent to 1 cycle of 100% DoD. The DoD of a battery is the inverse of the SoC and can be represented as the SoC subtracted from 100% charge ($1 - \text{SoC}$). We can calculate the cost per cycle of a battery as a fraction of the battery capital cost and the number of charge circles [203]. The cost per cycle b^{pc} of a battery and total degradation cost C^{deg} can be expressed as

$$b^{pc} = \frac{C^{bat}}{L_c}, \quad (3.1)$$

$$C^{deg} = b^{pc} \cdot \text{SoC}, \quad (3.2)$$

where C^{bat} is the battery capital cost in British Pounds (£) and L_c is the number of charges cycles. The linear estimation for capacity degradation of battery energy storage could render non-negligible (explicit and implicit) errors. Taking these factors into consideration, it is impractical to use a linear model to represent battery degradation cost. However, we can take the linear estimation as a reference model to benchmark the performance of the other models.

DoD is an important factor in charge cycle estimation because the relationship

between different DoD cycles and equivalent 100% DoD cycles is not linear [204]. For every DoD level, the value of the battery lifetime throughput L_T , measured in kWh, can be expressed as

$$L_T = L_c \cdot v^{cap} \cdot DoD, \quad (3.3)$$

where v^{cap} is the battery capacity and DoD is the DoD for which L_c was determined [205]. Based on the relationship between DoD and charge cycle, the battery degradation cost per kWh b^d can be expressed as

$$b^d = \frac{C^{bat}}{L_T}. \quad (3.4)$$

For an EV to participate in EVaaS energy trade, sufficient energy has to be stored in the battery. The energy stored in the battery could be self-generated or purchased. Based on this, the EV incurs a charge cost C^{ch} . From the charge cost, the valuation of energy unit can be expressed as

$$\bar{\mu} = \frac{C^{ch}}{v^{avail}}, \quad (3.5)$$

where v^{avail} is the available energy in the EV battery. For EV to avoid making financial losses, the discharge cost should cover the charge cost and compensate battery degradation. This can be expressed as

$$C^{dis} > C^{ch} + C^{deg}. \quad (3.6)$$

This ensures battery related liabilities do not become financial burden to EV owners.

3.2.3 Design Targets

In this chapter, key properties of the VCG mechanism such as truthfulness and individual rationality, as well as bidder satisfaction, are main targets. Hence, the proposed auction mechanism should be designed to achieve the following properties.

Truthfulness: An auction is truthful or incentive-compatible if participating EVs achieve maximum utility by revealing the true value of the energy stored in their batteries. In other words, the bid submitted by participating EVs equal their private valuation, i.e., $\mu = \bar{\mu}$, where μ is the energy unit bid and $\bar{\mu}$ is the valuation of energy unit. This property ensures that EVs cannot improve their utility by either bidding lower or higher than their true valuations; thus, preventing market manipulations.

Individual Rationality: An auction is individually rational if the utility of participating EVs is nonnegative whether they win or lose, i.e., $U \geq 0$, where U is the utility of EV. This property guarantees that no auction winner is paid less than what it bids; thus, ensuring EVs will not be worse off after EVaaS participation.

Bidder Satisfaction: An auction is satisfactory if participating EVs can enforce their energy trading conditions. This property guarantees that no bidder will be subjected to sell an undesirable amount of energy; thus, ensuring that the accepted bid volume from auction winners is within desirable limits, i.e., $v^{min} \leq v \leq v^{max}$, where v is the desirable amount of tradable energy, v^{min} and v^{max} are the lower and upper bounds, respectively.

3.3 VCG-Based Auction for EV-CL Association

We consider an auction model for EV-CL association. Let $i = \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$ denote a set of EVs within the microgrid which are available to participate in EVaaS operation. We assume there are much more EVs than the CL energy demand. The auction starts with the CL announcing its energy demand and location information to the aggregator which acts as an auctioneer. The auctioneer distributes a request for energy to EVs within the microgrid. The i th EV sends a four-tuple bid $b_i = (d_i, \mu_i, v_i^{min}, v_i^{max})$ to the auctioneer, where d_i denotes the estimated transportation distance between the i th EV and CL, in km; μ_i denotes energy unit cost of the i th EV, measured in British Pounds (£) per kWh; v_i^{min} denotes the minimum tradeable energy of the i th EV, in kWh; v_i^{max} denotes the maximum tradeable energy of the i th EV, in kWh. The auctioneer then determines the winning bids and the corresponding payments. The auction process is carried out in two stages: winner determination stage and price determination stage. The auction winner is derived in the winner determination stage and the payment to the auction winner is actualised in the price determination stage.

3.3.1 Winner Determination

Considering the winner determination problem is an optimisation problem with binary and continuous variables and nonlinear functions in the objective function and constraints, we formulate it as a mixed integer non-linear programming (MINLP) problem. Let α_i denote the binary variable, where $\alpha_i = 1$ if the i th EV wins the auction and 0 otherwise. The objective is to minimise the energy cost of EVs balancing CL demand, provided the energy stored in

the EV batteries is sufficient. The energy cost includes the transportation cost of EVs from its current location to the CL. For EVs to exchange energy with CL, they would have to transport the energy to the CL location. Energy is consumed during transportation and this needs to be accounted for. The energy consumption of driving EV is influenced by a number of factors such as vehicle type, road topology, driving patterns, traffic, weather variables, trip distance, etc [206]. Based on this, we assume an average energy consumption rate of 0.2 kWh per kilometre distance driven. Hence, the required energy for transportation of the i th EV v_i^{trans} can be expressed as the average consumption rate multiplied by the distance between the i th EV and CL, i.e., $v_i^{trans} = e_{cr}d_i$. The winner determination problem can be formulated as follows

$$\min_{\alpha_i, v_i} \sum_{i=1}^N \mu_i (v_i + v_i^{trans}) \alpha_i \quad (3.7)$$

Subject to

$$\sum_{i=1}^N v_i \alpha_i = V \quad (3.7a)$$

$$v_i^{min} \leq v_i + v_i^{trans} \leq v_i^{max} \quad (3.7b)$$

Constraint (3.7a) ensures the energy from auction winners v_i equals the CL energy demand V . Constraint (3.7b) ensures that the requested energy is within the limits of the i th EV.

3.3.2 Price Determination

In VCG mechanism, we determine the payment of each EV based on the harm it causes to other participants. From the winner determination stage, the energy cost of the i th EV is represented by C_i , which is the cost of per kWh energy multiplied by the requested energy ($C_i = \mu_i(v_i + v_i^{trans})$). The payment made to the i th EV can be calculated as

$$\rho_i = \min \underbrace{\sum_{k \neq i} C_k}_{\text{without } i\text{th EV}} - \underbrace{\sum_{k \neq i} C_k^\delta}_{\text{with } i\text{th EV}} . \quad (3.8)$$

In (3.8) k serves as an iterative factor which iterates through all the values excluding the i th EV, δ is the set of winning bidders chosen in (3.7). The left part of the equation represents the total energy cost for other participants when the i th EV is not participating, while the right part represents the total energy cost for the other participants when the i th EV participates.

The utility of each EV is the difference between its valuation and final payment (after price determination). The utility of the i th EV is calculated as follows

$$U_i = \rho_i - C_i. \quad (3.9)$$

While the winning bidders from the winner determination stage are guaranteed to make profit, the utility of the losing bidders is 0, i.e., $U_i > 0$ if $\alpha_i = 1$ and $U_i = 0$ if $\alpha_i = 0$.

3.3.3 Auction Algorithm

We develop an algorithm that finds the successful bidders and corresponding payment to the auction winners. The proposed strategy is effective in selecting EVs with minimum energy cost. The algorithm starts with computing N EVs and their four-tuple bids b_i . The CL energy demand V is also obtained. The transportation distance of the i th EV d_i is used to compute the required energy for transportation of the i th EV $v_i^{trans} = e_{cr}d_i$. The EVs are sorted in non-decreasing order of their energy unit cost, i.e., $\mu_1 \leq \mu_2 \leq \dots \leq \mu_N$. A counter for energy demand of CL C_V is initialised. Out of the list of EV to CL links, find EV-CL association with the lowest energy cost. The tradeable energy of the i th EV is verified such that $v_i^{min} \leq v_i + v_i^{trans} \leq v_i^{max}$. The energy balance constraint (3.7a) is then verified such that $C_V + v_i = V$. If all requirements are satisfied, the decision variable is modified as $\alpha = 1$ and the counter is updated accordingly. The process repeats until the list ends or the resources ends that can be tracked using the counter. VCG payment rule is applied to determine the payment of the i th EV. The energy cost without the i th EV C_k and with the i th EV C_k^* is derived. This is then used to compute the payment to the auction winners ρ_i . The procedure is summarised in Algorithm 3.1.

As mentioned earlier in section 3.2, bidder satisfaction is a key design feature of the proposed auction mechanism. By applying constraint (3.7b) in the algorithm, winning bidders do not experience any inconveniences beyond their acceptable levels. In other words, this constraint protects bidders from unfair trade conditions, which is common in centralised models where the aggregator finds the optimal solution at the expense of participating EVs. Without constraint (3.7b), the optimisation problem (3.7) will produce the optimal solution; therefore, Algorithm 3.1 ensures that the energy trading conditions of

Algorithm 3.1 Winner and Price Determination

Input: $N, b_i = (d_i, \mu_i, v_i^{min}, v_i^{max}), V, \alpha_i = 0$ **Output:** $\alpha_i = 1, v_i, \rho_i$ **Winner Determination**

- 1: Make a list of CL and EVs within the Area.
- 2: Calculate the required energy for transportation of EVs $v_i^{trans} = e_{cr}d_i$.
- 3: Sort μ_i in non-descending order.
- 4: Initialise: $C_V = 0$
- 5: **while** list of CL to EVs is not empty **do**
- 6: Find EV-CL association with the least energy cost in (3.7).
- 7: **if** $v_i^{min} \leq v_i + v_i^{trans} \leq v_i^{max}$ and $C_V + v_i = V$ **then**
- 8: Update $\alpha_i = 1$ and $C_V = C_V + v_i$
- 9: **else**
- 10: **break**
- 11: **end if**
- 12: **end while**

Price Determination

- 13: Calculate the energy cost without the i th EV C_k (3.8).
 - 14: Calculate the energy cost with the i th EV C_k^δ (3.8).
 - 15: Compute payment ρ_i for the i th EV based on (3.8).
 - 16: **return** α_i, v_i, ρ_i
-

winning bidders are satisfied, while producing a solution that is close to the optimal solution.

3.4 Energy Exchange Scheduling for EV-CL

Association

3.4.1 EV Modeling

EV battery capacity indicates the maximum amount of energy that can be extracted from the battery in a single discharge. We define the SoC of the EV battery as the ratio of the available energy to the battery capacity. The SoC of the i th EV can be mathematically represented as

$$SoC_i = \frac{v_i^{avail}}{v_i^{cap}}, \quad (3.10)$$

where v_i^{avail} is the available energy of the i th EV and v_i^{cap} is the battery capacity of the i th EV. To prolong the life of the EV battery and protect it from degradation, deep discharge should be avoided. After discharging, the remaining energy should cover the energy requirements for battery protection and EV transportation. The maximum tradeable energy v_i^{max} included in the bid ensures that the battery is protected from discharging beyond its user-specified minimum SoC. Based on the accepted amount of energy v_i derived from Algorithm 3.1, the minimum SoC of the i th EV can be mathematically represented as

$$SoC_i^{min} = \frac{v_i^{avail} - (v_i + v_i^{trans})}{v_i^{cap}}. \quad (3.11)$$

3.4.2 CL Modeling

A load profile is a representation of the energy usage of a consumer, showing the demand variation over a period of time. The load profile of the CL is essential to determining the discharging power of EVs at each time slot. The load behaviour is influenced by several factors such as time, day, weather condition, season, economic factors and random effect. The CL power demand can be forecasted using techniques such as regression method, time-series method, fuzzy logic, neural networks and similar-day approach [102, 103]. The similar-day approach is adopted to estimate the CL power demand at each time slot by averaging the power demand of the same time slot from historical data with similar characteristics (e.g., day of week, weather, etc.). The estimated CL power demand can be expressed as

$$D_t = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=1}^M \widehat{D}_{m,t} + \Delta D, \quad (3.12)$$

$$\Delta D = \widehat{D}_t - \widetilde{D}_t, \quad (3.13)$$

where M is the number of data points selected, $D_{m,t}$ is the measurement obtained in the m th similar day at time slot t , ΔD is the bias caused by the forecasting errors, \widehat{D}_t is the actual observed CL power demand at time slot t and \widetilde{D}_t is the forecasted CL power demand at time slot t .

We can calculate the CL energy demand as the sum of the CL power demand over a time period, where the total time period T is divided into time slots such that the interval length is given by $\Delta t = 1$ h. The CL energy demand can be mathematically represented as

$$V = \sum_{t=1}^T D_t. \quad (3.14)$$

3.4.3 EV Discharging Scheduling

We consider the discharging scheduling of physically distant EVs within the microgrid, where EVs would need to travel to the CL to supply energy. The scheduling for discharging of EVs is operating cost minimisation problem to determine the best schedule for discharging EVs to supply power to CL at each time slot. Let T indicate the total scheduling intervals, while t defines the value of each parameter or variable at any time instant. We can calculate the operating cost as the sum of the energy, transportation and battery degradation costs. The EV discharging scheduling problem can be formulated as follows

$$\min_{P_i} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{t=1}^T \rho_i P_{i,t} + \sum_{i=1}^N \rho_i v_i^{trans} + \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{t=1}^T b_i^d P_{i,t} \quad (3.15)$$

Subject to

$$\sum_{i=1}^N P_{i,t} = D_t \quad (3.15a)$$

$$P_i^{min} \leq P_{i,t} \leq P_i^{max} \quad (3.15b)$$

$$SoC_{i,t} = SoC_{i,t-1} - \frac{P_{i,t}/\eta^{dis} \times \Delta t}{v_i^{cap}} \quad (3.15c)$$

$$SoC_i^{min} \leq SoC_{i,t} \leq SoC_i^{max} \quad (3.15d)$$

The first term of (3.15) represents the energy cost, the second term represents the transportation cost, and the third term represents the battery degradation cost. Constraint (3.15a) is the power balance equation which ensures that power from discharging EVs at time slot t equals the CL power demand D_t at time slot t . Constraint (3.15b) ensures that the discharging power at time slot t is within the limits of the i th EV, where P_i^{min} and P_i^{max} are the minimum and maximum discharging power of the i th EV, respectively. Constraint (3.15c) indicates the SoC of the i th EV at time slot t , where η^{dis} is the discharging efficiency and Δt is the length of a single time interval. Constraint (3.15d) ensures that the SoC at time slot t is within the limits of the i th EV for the protection of battery, where SoC_i^{min} and SoC_i^{max} are the minimum and maximum SoC of the i th EV battery, respectively.

3.4.4 Scheduling Algorithm

We develop an algorithm that schedules EV discharging power while minimising the total operating cost of the EVs. The algorithm starts with computing the auction winners α_i and their corresponding payments ρ_i , required energy for transportation v_i^{trans} , battery degradation cost b_i^d , minimum SoC SoC_i^{min} , minimum discharging power P_i^{min} and maximum discharging power P_i^{max} . The CL power demand D_t is forecasted using similar-day approach (3.12). The total time period T is also obtained. One counter for power demand of CL C_P is initialised. The SoC_i of the i th EV (3.10) is calculated. If the SoC_i is more than the minimum SoC of the i th EV SoC_i^{min} , the optimal discharging schedule is determined by solving the scheduling problem (3.15). The discharging power of the i th EV $P_{i,t}$ is verified such that $P_i^{min} \leq P_{i,t} \leq P_i^{max}$, the power balance constraints (3.15a) is then verified such that $C_P + P_{i,t} = D_t$. If the requirements are satisfied, the i th EV is scheduled to perform discharging with discharging power $P_{i,t}$ at time slot t and the counter is updated, as well as the time slot and $SoC_{i,t}$ (3.15c). If the SoC_i is at the minimum SoC of the i th EV SoC_i^{min} , there would be no discharging for the i th EV. The process repeats over the time period T or until the resources ends that can be tracked using the counter. The procedure is summarised in Algorithm 3.2.

The bidder satisfaction property guarantees that EVs would not experience inconveniences beyond their user-specified levels. By applying constraint (3.15d) in the algorithm, which reinforces constraint (3.7b), EVs can reserve a fraction of their battery capacity to cover the energy requirements for battery protection and EV transportation. In other words, this constraint prolongs battery life, prevents deep discharge and ensures that EVs do not run out of range. To minimise range anxiety, the minimum SoC should include a proportional range safety buffer of up to 30% of battery capacity.

Algorithm 3.2 Scheduling Algorithm**Input:** $N, T, \alpha_i, v_i^{trans}, \rho_i, b_i^d, SoC_i^{min}, P_i^{min}, P_i^{max}, D_t$ **Output:** $P_{i,t}$

- 1: Compute CL power demand D_t based on (3.12).
- 2: Make a list of auction winners α_i .
- 3: Initialise: $t = 0, C_P = 0$
- 4: Calculate initial SoC_i .
- 5: **for** $t = 1, \dots, T$ **do**
- 6: **while** the system is active **do**
- 7: Find the optimal discharging schedule in (3.15).
- 8: **if** $SoC_{i,t} > SoC_i^{min}$ and $P_i^{min} \leq P_{i,t} \leq P_i^{max}$ **then**
- 9: **if** $C_P + P_{i,t} = D_t$ **then**
- 10: Discharge i th EV with $P_{i,t}$.
- 11: Update $C_P = C_P + P_{i,t}$
- 12: Update $t = t + 1$
- 13: Compute $SoC_{i,t}$ based on (3.15c).
- 14: **end if**
- 15: **else**
- 16: No discharging for i th EV.
- 17: **end if**
- 18: **end while**
- 19: **end for**
- 20: **return** $P_{i,t}$

3.5 Numerical Results and Discussions

We consider a microgrid where the CL is seeking to buy energy from EVs with surplus energy. The number of participating EVs is Poisson distributed with an average density λ [207]. Based on the retail price of the Nissan Leaf replacement battery pack [208], battery cost of £5,000 is assigned to EVs. We consider an EV battery with 2,000 charge cycles at 100% DOD. Energy demand of the CL is uniformly chosen from [40 220] kWh. Energy unit cost of EVs is randomly distributed over [0.07 0.35] £/kWh. The randomness of EV energy unit cost replicates the real-world scenario where EVs have varied energy unit cost based on their charge cost. Minimum available energy in the range of [8 12] kWh and maximum available energy in the range of [18 25] kWh

FIGURE 3.2: Discharging schedule of EVs to fulfil CL demand.

FIGURE 3.3: Compensation for battery degradation during EV-CL interaction.

are randomly generated for EVs. The data of the EVs and CL and necessary parameters are passed to the algorithms to find the successful bidders and their corresponding payment, and then schedule discharging EVs accordingly. All simulations were performed using MATLAB.

Figure 3.2 shows the discharging schedule for EV-CL association. This illustrates a real-world scenario where discharging EVs supply energy during times of peak demand. Based on the load profile, the discharging power of associated EVs are scheduled to satisfy the hourly demand of the CL. Figure 3.3 shows the effect of the proposed battery degradation compensation paid to EV owners. It is observed that in every scenario without compensation EV owners make a significant loss. Without the battery degradation compensation, EV owners will always incur financial losses during EV-CL interaction, regardless of the incentives received from the pricing scheme. This may not motivate the EV owners to participate in EVaaS. By adding the monetary equivalent of battery losses to the charge cost, battery related liabilities are compensated. This demonstrates that in the absence of battery degradation compensation, EVaaS participation is not profitable for EV owners.

We evaluate the performances of the proposed allocation scheme (3.7) with the centralised scheme in [54] and single bidding mechanism in [12]. In order to minimise the energy cost for the CL, [54] and [12] subject EVs to sell an undesirable amount of energy. The single bidding approach formulated in [12] is similar to our proposed allocation scheme. However, our allocation scheme is formulated as a MINLP problem where the tradeable energy is a continuous variable bounded by minimum and maximum discharging energy limits for each EV, while [12] considers only a binary variable for their integer linear programming (ILP) problem. We consider [12] as our reference scheme and use it to study the performance of our proposed allocation scheme. Different scenarios were considered in Figure 3.4 with respect to CL demand, and for each scenario, the total bids of the auction winners are computed under the different allocation schemes. Our proposed allocation scheme outperforms the reference scheme in every scenario. As expected, the centralised scheme would typically give a better performance than a distributed scheme; however,

FIGURE 3.4: Bids of auction winners under different schemes.

FIGURE 3.5: Payments of auction winners versus EV distribution density.

our proposed allocation scheme follows the centralised scheme closely in each scenario and ensures auction winners sell a reasonable amount of energy.

Figure 3.5 shows the bids and final payment made to EVs for different densities of EV distribution. For a CL demand of 60 kWh, λ is uniformly chosen from [0.1 0.9]. Payments obtained for λ in [0.1 0.3], [0.4 0.6] and [0.7 0.9]

FIGURE 3.6: Performance on bidder satisfaction.

are averaged to form the low, medium and high EV distribution densities, respectively. The low density represents areas with a low number of EVs (e.g., rural areas), the high density represents areas with a high number of EVs (e.g., urban areas) and the medium density represents areas in-between the rural and urban areas. It is observed that the total payment to the auction winners decreases with an increase in EV distribution density. This can be attributed to the number of EVs participating in the auction. When there are less EVs, the cost gap between progressive lower bids is higher compared to a scenario that has more EVs. When more EVs join the auction, the cost for the CL decreases due to the increased competition between participating EVs. This demonstrates that EVaaS will benefit the EVs more in rural areas, while the CL will save cost in urban areas.

To evaluate the performance on bidder satisfaction, we introduce the bidder satisfaction ratio metric. The bidder satisfaction ratio is defined as the ratio of the amount of energy that the bidder sells in the auction to their maximum tradeable energy. We assume that all bidders want to sell their maximum tradeable energy; thus, we average the satisfaction ratio of successful bidders

FIGURE 3.7: Performance on truthfulness.

that are not able to sell their maximum tradeable energy. Figure 3.6 shows the bidder satisfaction ratio across the different EV distribution densities with respect to CL demand, where 0.5 is the satisfactory level. It can be observed that the bidder satisfaction ratio in our proposed scheme is above satisfactory level and outperforms the reference scheme in every scenario. While the auction in the reference scheme [12] aims at the minimisation of energy cost of the CL. This means that the auction in the reference scheme is carried out at the expense of the bidders, which is responsible for the bidder satisfaction ratio falling below satisfactory level.

We evaluate the performance of the proposed VCG-based auction for EV-CL association on truthfulness and individual rationality. Figure 3.7 shows the performance on guaranteeing the truthfulness of bidders. We study the changes in utility under conditions of a random EV submitting untruthful bids and its private valuation. When the EV increases its bid to £0.29/kWh, it loses the auction and its utility is 0. This shows that the EV cannot improve its utility by misrepresenting its valuation, thus protecting the fairness and efficiency of the trade.

FIGURE 3.8: Performance on individual rationality.

Figure 3.8 shows the performance on guaranteeing individual rationality of bidders. For a CL of 200 kWh, the submitted bids of the auction winners, as well as their corresponding payments, are presented. It can be observed that the final payments to auction winners is no less than their bids, which means every auction winner has a nonnegative utility. Overall, the proposed mechanism verifies the theoretical analysis on truthfulness and individual rationality and better incentivizes participating EVs.

3.6 Summary

In this chapter, an incentivized approach for energy trading between EVs and CL in a microgrid is proposed. The EV-CL association problem is formulated as a one-sided auction, where EVs bid to trade their surplus energy. The model considers several practical constraints such as energy demand and charging station limit. The approach further integrates battery degradation cost to ensure EV owners are compensated for battery degradation incurred

during EV-CL interaction. VCG payment rule is applied to determine the payments to selected EVs. Numerical results reveal that our proposed approach achieves a performance which is comparable to those given by reference schemes, guarantees bidder satisfaction and validates theoretical analysis on economic properties of truthfulness and individual rationality. The next chapter investigates carbon emissions alongside economic benefit maximisation in EV-CL association.

Chapter 4

Combined Economic Emission Based Resource Allocation

4.1 Introduction

The economic aspect in chapter 3 is examined alongside the emissions aspect. Unlike focusing on economic benefit maximisation in the previous chapter, carbon emission is also considered in the association between discharging electric vehicles (EVs) and critical load (CL). This chapter presents a combined economic emission optimisation model for energy cost and carbon emission minimisation. This chapter is based on results in [137] and addresses the fourth research question of this thesis.

4.1.1 Background

In the conventional way of transporting energy (from generation to consumption) through the grid, a loss of about 2% occurs over the transmission network

and a further 8% over the distribution network [209]. These network losses lead to increased energy costs and account for about 1.5% of the greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in the UK [209]. Alternatively, EVs can store, transport and supply energy directly to the CLs. EVs can also be deployed to meet short-term energy demands of CLs such as pop-up hospitals and evacuation centres set up during emergency situations, which may not be met by regular supply [161]. By transmitting energy through EVs, power network losses will be reduced [210], which will lead to reduced energy costs and GHG emissions. Most existing studies focus only on economic benefit maximisation [55]. However, due to growing environmental concerns, strategies that automatically account for environmental constraints are desirable.

Currently, there are limited existing studies on combined economic emission (CEE) problem incorporating physically distant EVs for balancing demand-supply mismatch in microgrids. Formulation of CEE problems as described in the existing literature [16–19] differs with regards to the type of criterion function, conversion factor used to formulate the multi-criteria optimisation function and practical constraints. A weight factor-based optimisation model for cost and emission reductions in a smart grid by maximum utilisation of EVs and renewable energy resources (RESs) is presented in [16]. In [17], plug-in hybrid electric vehicles (PHEVs) are exploited as mobile energy storage unit involving unit commitment model, where the optimal plug-in capacities of PHEVs and the scheme are obtained through a mixed integer programming algorithm, considering cost coefficients of emission. An optimisation model using weighted sum method is proposed in [18] to solve the economic dispatch problem on a generation system, considering EVs expected future demand. Another optimisation model using weighted sum method for dynamic economic/emission dispatch including EVs for peak shaving and valley filling is proposed in [19], considering EV battery degradation cost.

The conventional centralised dispatching approaches in the literature do not consider physically distant, ideally EVs are distributed over the local region and would need to travel to the CL to supply energy. The optimisation models in the literature are different from ours, while they solve a dispatch problem, ours finds optimal association of disperse EVs with CL. Most contributions to CCE problem focus on optimal dispatch of power generators; to the best of our knowledge, this is the first contribution that exploits physically distant EVs to provide capacity on-demand to fulfil CL demand in microgrids.

4.1.2 Our Contributions

This work is an extension of the work [54], where the electric vehicle as a service (EVaaS) framework is introduced and EV-CL association is modeled as a mixed integer linear programming (MILP) problem. In this chapter, the proposed CEE problem is considered as a mixed integer non-linear programming (MINLP) problem because it has nonlinear functions in the objective function and constraints with binary and continuous variables. Unlike focusing on economic benefit maximisation, we also consider carbon emissions as a second objective function. The main contributions of this chapter can be summarised as follows.

- We propose CEE optimisation to exploit the trade-off between emissions and operational costs in EV-CL association. We study EV battery degradation and the communication requirements for successful EV-CL interaction. The model integrates battery degradation cost, so they do not become financial liabilities from EVaaS participation.
- We then formulate the CEE problem as a bi-objective optimisation problem, which is subject to practical constraints such as energy demand,

cost budget, emission limit and charging station limit. Towards solving the bi-objective problem, we introduce carbon price to convert it into a single objective function and ensure consistency of metric units.

- The proposed model is compared with traditional strategies and distributed energy resources (DERs) such as energy storage systems (ESSs), diesel generators (DGs) and mobile emergency generators (MEGs) via numerical results. The strategy showed reductions in operational costs and carbon emissions; thus, EVaaS is cost efficient for demand response.

The remainder of the chapter is organised as follows. The EVaaS system framework is described in Section 4.2. In Section 4.3, the CEE optimisation problem is formulated and a detailed explanation of the optimisation algorithm is presented. Simulation and numerical results are analysed in Section 4.4. Conclusions are drawn in section 4.5.

4.2 EVaaS System Framework

The EVaaS model shown in Figure 4.1 consists of EVs, CLs, smart meters and microgrid central controller (MGCC). The subsystems communicate with the microgrid through a communication network to effectively carry out tasks and collectively achieve an objective. The MGCC monitors and controls subsystems to ensure overall system efficiency [211]. Microgrids demonstrate homogeneous characteristics to system of systems, thus making it convenient to integrate its subsystems in an system of systems framework [212]. Now enclosed in the system of systems framework, the microgrid can actualise its functions in a coordinated manner, while strategically utilizing its subsystems to accomplish its objectives.

FIGURE 4.1: EVaaS system model.

The conventional centralised dispatching approach in the literature is not ideal for EVaaS application, as a result a two-stage model comprising association and dispatch stages could be one way to model the combined problem. The operation strategy for CL demand fulfilment with physically distant EVs is a non-convex and multi-objective optimisation problem which is generally hard to solve in reasonable computational times, even for small-sized systems [213]. Thus, the problem can be decomposed into association and dispatch problems. The association problem associates EVs with CL, while the dispatch problem schedules associated EVs to discharge energy. This chapter focuses on the optimal association of EVs with CL for CL demand fulfilment in microgrids. The dispatch strategy is out of scope and will be investigated in our future study, where these two problems will be addressed sequentially.

Communication between EVs and the EVaaS infrastructure is enabled with a mix of technologies discussed in Section 2.4.1. During EVaaS interaction,

information on EV battery capacity, current location of EV, CL demand, location of CL and other similar information need to be available. Hence, data communication is the fundamental step to optimise the energy resources distributed over the local region and achieve the best performance. Since the decision making is always based on updated information, the system relies on real-time, high-precision and low-latency communication networks to develop effective optimal EV association decisions. Here, EVs within a defined area are selected, based on emission and operational costs. However, issues including data collision (due to high EV deployment scale) and transmission failure (due to insufficient coverage) are usually inevitable. In the worst case, the CL would select EVs with shortest geographic distance as a backup scheme, if optimum EV association is not obtained from the system [214]. EVs are then associated based on first come first served (FCFS) scheme. The impact of communication failure in the system will be analyzed in our numerical study.

4.2.1 Energy Efficiency of EV Battery

Coulombic efficiency of EV battery can be seen as a measure of how much of the stored energy is measurable as electrical energy. Since no chemical or physical process can obtain 100% energy efficiency, more energy is always used to charge the battery than can be extracted from it. Hence, the energy efficiency of the battery can be expressed as the ratio of charge output to charge input. The amount of energy received by the CL depends on the discharging efficiency of the battery. This can be mathematically represented as

$$v = v^{rated} \cdot \eta_{dis}, \quad (4.1)$$

where v^{rated} is the rated battery capacity, in kWh, v is the actual volume of energy that can be discharged by the EV battery, in kWh; η_{dis} is the discharge efficiency of the battery.

The energy efficiency of the battery decreases as the number of charge cycle increases, where a charge cycle is a complete charge and discharge process on the battery. As a result of natural limitations, the EV battery usage is limited to a fixed number of charge cycles, over time the capacity will gradually fall and its performance will decrease significantly.

4.2.2 EVaaS Revenue

For an EV to participate in EVaaS, the battery has to be charged. Assuming the EV battery has a 85% efficiency, 15% of the supplied energy to the battery by the grid or alternative source is always lost. The energy supplier will bill the EV according to the amount of energy supplied and not the actual amount of energy received. Therefore, the total supplied energy cost can be mathematically represented as

$$C^c = \omega_{off-peak} \cdot E_{off-peak} + \omega_{peak} \cdot E_{peak}, \quad (4.2)$$

where C^c is the charge cost for energy supplied to the EV, measured in British Pounds (£) per kWh; $\omega_{off-peak}$ is the unit energy cost during off-peak hour, measured in British Pounds (£) per kWh; ω_{peak} is the unit energy cost during peak hour, measured in British Pounds (£) per kWh; $E_{off-peak}$ is the total energy supplied during off-peak hour, in kWh; E_{peak} is the total energy supplied during peak hour, in kWh.

The cost of the energy stored in the battery is the sum of charge cost and battery degradation cost, that is

$$C^{val} = C^c + B^c. \quad (4.3)$$

For EVs to avoid making financial losses, the discharge cost should not be less than the valued cost of energy, i.e., $C^d \not\leq C^{val}$, where C^d is the discharge cost. This ensures EVs are not worse off after EVaaS participation.

4.2.3 EV Emission

Unlike conventional vehicles, EVs do not produce any exhaust emission, however they can still contribute to higher carbon footprint. Charging EV from a grid with high coal usage in its energy mix will result in a higher carbon footprint compared to charging EV from a grid that generates electricity from predominately renewable energy [215]. EV emission is calculated according to the conversion factors for the electricity supplied to the grid [216]. EV emission E_m can be mathematically expressed as

$$E_m = \sigma \cdot e_f, \quad (4.4)$$

where σ is the activity data and e_f is the emission factor, expressed in term of one unit of carbon. A notable factor associated with grid consumed energy is the emission associated with grid losses. The grid losses occur while getting electricity from generation stations to the load, in this case, charged EVs. Therefore, emissions from energy consumption can be calculated by adding together the energy generation and the transmission and distribution values. Including emissions associated with transmission and distribution losses is optional, however it is considered best practice. The next section presents the CEE optimisation problem for associating EVs with CL.

4.3 Problem Formulation

4.3.1 Problem Formulation

Traditionally, EVs are associated to CLs using economic benefit maximisation as the criterion [54, 217]. However, the cost-effective association does not lead to minimum emission, likewise, minimal emission association does not lead to minimum operating cost. The aim of emission-based association is to determine EVs with the least carbon-emission cost. The two criteria are in a trade-off relationship and are contradictory to each other. This bi-objective problem can be solved using methods such as weighted sum method, ϵ -constraint method, lexicographic method, global criterion method, weighted metric method and evolutionary method [218, 219]. But for simplicity, we use the weighted sum method. By appropriate manipulations, the operational cost and emissions can be placed on a comparable basis which results in a single suitability function encapsulating both costs and emissions. When environmental concerns are added as a second objective to the economic association problem, it becomes a CEE optimisation problem.

Considering a microgrid where EVs and CLs are uniformly distributed in a square region of Area A_r . We model their locations as a binomial point process (BPP) [207]. This provides random distribution points of EVs and CLs denoted as (x_i, y_i) and (x_j, y_j) , respectively, where $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, N_{EV}\}$ and $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, N_{CL}\}$. From the fixed positions of EVs and CLs, the transportation distance $d_{ij} = |x_i - x_j| + |y_i - y_j|$ of i -th EV from j -th CL is derived. The Manhattan distance function computes the travel distance between EVs and CL if a grid-like path is followed. The grid-layout depicts streets of a city in a real-world scenario. The problem formulation is as follows:

4.3.1.1 Cost Function

The cost function models the operational cost of the deploying discharging EVs in a microgrid to fulfill CL demand. The operational cost here includes the energy cost and the transportation cost of EVs from its current location to the CL. The energy cost is determined by the obtainable energy from the EV battery, which considers the discharging efficiency of the battery (4.1). The transportation cost is determined by the travel distance. The cost function is formulated as

$$C_{ij} = EC_i \cdot v_{ij} + TC_i \cdot d_{ij}, \quad (4.5)$$

where v_{ij} denotes the amount of energy of the i -th EV required by the j -th CL, in kWh; EC_i denotes the unit energy cost of the i -th EV, measured in British Pounds (£) per kWh; d_{ij} denotes the estimated transportation distance from i -th EV to j -th CL, in km; TC_i denotes the unit transportation cost of the i -th EV, measured in British Pounds (£) per km.

4.3.1.2 Emission Function

The emission function models the total emission, in kilograms of carbon dioxide equivalent (kg CO_{2e}), from deploying discharging EVs in a microgrid to power CLs. From (4.4), the emissions model can be modified to include energy consumption and transportation emission for EVs. Energy consumption emission is the total energy consumption (electricity or fuel) multiplied by the emission factor (electricity or fuel). Transportation emission is the total activity of vehicle category (in km) multiplied by the emission factor. The emission function can be formulated as

$$E_{ij} = ef_c(v_{ij} + e_{cr} \cdot d_{ij}), \quad (4.6)$$

where ef_c denotes energy consumption emission factor, measured in kg CO₂e per kWh; e_{cr} denotes energy consumption rate, measured in kWh per km.

EVs do not produce any exhaust emission during transportation, however, energy is consumed during transportation and this needs to be accounted for in the emission function. The energy consumption rate e_{cr} denotes the amount of energy used per unit distance. The energy consumption rate differs by EV manufacturer, EV model, driving patterns (speed and acceleration), weather variables, road type, trip distance and other factors [206]. Hence, an average energy consumption rate of 0.2 kWh per kilometre distance driven has been assumed in this chapter. It is assumed EVs have been charged from the utility grid, therefore the energy consumption emission factor from [216] has been used in this chapter.

4.3.1.3 Combined Economic Emission

The CEE function aims to optimise the two objective functions. This problem can be formulated by including emission minimisation as an objective along with operational cost minimisation. The bi-objective optimisation problem is formulated as follows

$$F_{ij} = [C_{ij}, E_{ij}] = C_{ij} + cp \cdot E_{ij}, \quad (4.7)$$

where the carbon price cp is the amount that must be paid to emit 1 kg of CO₂e. The conversion process is actualised using the carbon price and the effect of emissions can be related to the cost. The EU ETS stipulates the

emission allowances and sets the carbon price [220]. To illustrate the proposed model, a carbon price of £0.5/kg CO₂e is assumed in this chapter.

4.3.1.4 Association Problem Formulation

The association between EVs and CL is an MINLP problem. It has a non-convex objective function and involves non-linear constraints with binary and continuous variables, i.e. A_{ij} and v_{ij} , respectively. Let A_{ij} denote a binary variable that shows the association of EVs and CLs as

$$A_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } i\text{-th EV is assigned with } j\text{-th CL,} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (4.8)$$

The objective is to associate optimum EVs with CLs such that the sum CEE cost is minimised. Such a problem can be formulated as

$$\min_{A_{ij}, v_{ij}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{EV}} \sum_{j=1}^{N_{CL}} F_{ij} \cdot A_{ij} \quad (4.9)$$

Subject to

$$\sum_{i=1}^{N_{EV}} v_{ij} \cdot A_{ij} = V_j, \quad \forall j \quad (4.9a)$$

$$0 \leq v_{ij} \leq v_{ij}^{max} \quad (4.9b)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^{N_{EV}} \sum_{j=1}^{N_{CL}} C_{ij} \cdot A_{ij} \leq C_{bud}, \quad \forall i, j \quad (4.9c)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^{N_{EV}} \sum_{j=1}^{N_{CL}} E_{ij} \cdot A_{ij} \leq E_{lim}, \quad \forall i, j \quad (4.9d)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^{N_{EV}} A_{ij} \leq CS_j, \quad \forall j. \quad (4.9e)$$

The energy supplied by the EVs must satisfy CL demand and the system losses, however there is no loss of load being considered. This constraint can be written as constraint (4.9a), where the total available energy from associated EVs v_{ij} equals the CL demand V_j . Constraint (4.9b) ensures that the requested energy from EV should not exceed the maximum energy limit v_{ij}^{max} . The total cost for resource allocation should be within a given budget of the distribution system. This constraint can be written as constraint (4.9c), where C_{bud} is the maximum budget for EV allocation in the system. Constraint (4.9d) is the emission allowance for the given system, which gives the emission limit E_{lim} . The emission allowance satisfies the carbon cap, which is set on the total amount of GHG that can be emitted by installations covered by the EU ETS [220]. This means the sum of emissions cannot exceed the emission limit E_{lim} . A limited number of discharging EVs can be connected to the system, considering the number of charging station. Then, constraint (4.9e) shows that j -th CL can maintain a maximum number of discharging EVs as per charging station limit CS_j . When EVs are associated with CL, power flow should be satisfied ensuring both active and reactive power are balanced. Variables such as discharging power of EVs should be within acceptable ranges. However, these constraints are not considered at the association stage. Considering all the above constraints, for fixed positions of the EVs and CLs, we search for the best possible association between them.

4.3.2 Optimisation Algorithm

The optimisation problem is an MINLP and we present here an efficient greedy solution that is designed to solve the CEE optimisation problem. The strategy here is to select the EVs with minimal CEE cost. The complete steps can be described as follows.

TABLE 4.1: Simulation Parameters

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
A_r	16 km ²	e_{cr}	0.2 kWh/km
D_{max}	4 km	$e f_c$	0.35156
N_{EV}	17	C_{bud}	£300
N_{CL}	1	E_{lim}	100 kg CO2e

Step 1: Compute the number of EVs and CL, and their distribution in a defined region. At this point, a snap shot of EVs and CL is obtained providing their positions (x_i, x_j) and (y_i, y_j) , respectively. This is used to compute the transportation distance d_{ij} of the EVs from the CL.

Step 2: The capacity of the EVs and the demand of the CL is also obtained, along with the cost budget, emission limit and charging station constraints.

Step 3: Four counters are initialised; maximum number of charging stations C_{CS} , energy demand of CL C_v , cost budget C_{Cb} and emission limit C_{El} . Out of the list of CL to EV links, the link that provides the minimum CEE, $\min(F_{ij})$ is chosen. The algorithm then verifies the constraints of energy balance (4.9a), cost budget (4.9c), emission limit (4.9d) and number of charging stations (4.9e) such that $C_v + v_{ij} \geq V$, $C_{Cb} + C_{ij} \leq C_{bud}$, $C_{El} + E_{ij} \leq E_{lim}$ and $C_{CS} + 1 \leq CS$, respectively.

Step 4: If the CL-EV pair pass the verification stage, they are then associated to each other and all four counters are updated. The process is repeated until the list ends or the resources ends that can be tracked using the four counters. The steps are summarised in Algorithm 4.1.

The next section presents the association of EVs with CL and the emission and cost benefit related numerical results for the EVaaS model, where EV is associated to CL during emergency response.

Algorithm 4.1 CEE Optimisation Algorithm

Input: N_{EV} , N_{CL} , V_j , C_{bud} , E_{lim} , CS **Output:** A_{ij} , v_{ij}

- 1: Make a list of CL and EVs within the Area A_r
 - 2: Calculate the distance d_{ij} between EVs and CL
 - 3: Initialise counters: $C_{CS} = 0$, $C_{Cb} = 0$, $C_{El} = 0$ and $C_v = 0$
 - 4: **while** list of CL to EVs is not empty **do**
 - 5: Find CL j and EV i with $\min(F_{ij})$
 - 6: **if** $C_v + v_{ij} \geq V$, $C_{Cb} + C_{ij} \leq C_{bud}$, $C_{El} + E_{ij} \leq E_{lim}$ and $C_{CS} \leq CS$ **then**
 - 7: Update $A_{ij} = 1$, $C_{CS} = C_{CS} + 1$, $C_v = C_v + v_{ij}$, $C_{Cb} = C_{Cb} + C_{ij}$ and $C_{El} = C_{El} + E_{ij}$
 - 8: **else**
 - 9: **break**
 - 10: **end if**
 - 11: **end while**
-

4.4 Numerical Results and Discussions

In this section, we present numerical results that validates the effectiveness of the proposed mechanism for optimum EV-CL association in microgrids. We evaluate and compare the performance of the proposed resource allocation scheme with traditional strategies [214, 217]. We analyse the performances of the proposed EVaaS model with several DERs described as follows.

- **Mobile Emergency Generator (MEG):** In this approach, a truck-mounted mobile emergency generator is dispatched to the CL [221]. A heavy good vehicle (HGV) is used to transport the diesel generator. The operating cost of MEGs includes the energy generation cost and the transportation cost. The MEG emission includes the energy consumption generated emission and the transportation emission from the HGV. The emission is determined by multiplying the activity (generation/transportation) by the emission factors in [216].

- Diesel Generator (DG): In this approach, a stationary diesel-powered generator supplies energy to the CL. The difference between DG and MEG is the exclusion of the HGV used for transportation. This means the transportation cost and emission are excluded in this case study.
- Energy Storage System (ESS): In this approach, energy is supplied to the CL from an ESS. The ESS is assumed to have charged from the electricity grid. Therefore, the emission is the same as that of the electricity grid.

For our simulation, we consider a microgrid where EVs and CL are BPP distributed in a square region of area $A_r = 16 \text{ km}^2$. In our simulation, the number of EVs and CL are fixed and for each simulation setting, 100 scenarios with different location of EVs and CL are generated to average the results. The maximum distance D_{max} of EV from CL is 4 km. We assume EVs are already charged at the time of association, thus random on-demand capacity between 15 kWh and 28 kWh are allotted to EVs, while discharging efficiency between 0.90 and 0.95 are randomly assigned to EVs. The randomness of EV battery capacity and discharging efficiency replicates the real-world scenario where EVs have varied on-demand capacity and discharging efficiency, respectively. Unit energy cost between £0.07/kWh and £0.12/kWh and unit transportation cost between £0.8/km and £1.3/km are randomly assigned to EVs. Different energy demand are allocated to CL for different scenarios. Considering EV and CL data, with battery capacity, discharge efficiency and coordinates of EVs, energy demand and coordinates for CL and other parameters defined in Table 4.1, the parameters for CL to EV association is calculated. Finally, the necessary parameters are passed to the algorithms to find the best possible association between CL and EVs by minimising the CEE optimisation problem (4.9).

FIGURE 4.2: The layout of random distribution and association of EVs and CL with constraints $V = 70$ kWh, $CS = 4$.

Figure 4.2 demonstrates one of the considered scenarios of distribution and association of EVs and CL. Figure 4.2a, 4.2b and 4.2c shows EVs associated with CL based on operational cost, emissions and CEE cost, respectively. Considering the variation of unit energy and unit transportation costs, a summation of energy and transportation costs will tend to focus the cost optimisation on the travel distance, since the unit energy cost is numerically smaller than

the unit transportation cost. On the other hand, the emission is not strongly distant related, i.e., minimising travel distance is not equivalent to minimising the emission function. This is demonstrated in 4.2b where the EVs with the least emission are not the same as the EVs with the shortest travel distance. The case study validates the capability of the proposed strategy and formulation to match EVs with CL, thus achieving better utilisation of EVs. Once optimal association of decision has been derived, EVs are then deployed to the assigned location to balance demand-supply mismatch.

Figure 4.3 shows the total emission and operational cost of associated EVs versus CL demand. Here, we compare the optimisation problem considering cost, emission and CEE functions. Overall all three give a good performance in comparison to other DERs considered in this study. Emission and cost functions give good performances for total emission and operational cost, respectively, while CEE optimisation gives a good trade off between the emissions and operational cost. The analysis will be covered in Figures 4.7 and 4.8. For a single value of CL demand and EV deployment scale, we have generated 100 different scenarios and then averaged the associated total emission and operational cost. Figures 4.3a and 4.3b show the total emission and operational cost, respectively, for different CL demand. Optimizing the emission function would typically give a better performances for total emission as seen in Figure 4.3a. However, the CEE optimisation produces a good trade off. At all CL demand, the CEE optimisation produces a better performance than cost function optimisation. At CL demand of 40 kWh and 100 kWh, the CEE optimisation produces a 5% improvement, while at CL demand of 70 kWh, it produces a 6% improvement. At every other CL demand, the CEE optimisation produces at least 3% improvement. In Figure 4.3b, the CEE optimisation produces the best results compared to the cost and emission functions. At CL

FIGURE 4.3: Emission and cost of associated EVs versus CL demand averaged over 100 scenarios.

demand of 70 kWh, the CEE optimisation produces a 3% and 6% improvement compared to the cost and emission functions. Similarly, at CL demand of 100 kWh, the CEE optimisation produces a 3% and 5% improvement. While at every other CL demand, the CEE optimisation produces at least 2% and 4% improvement compared to the cost and emission functions, respectively. As expected, it can be seen that the total cost considering CEE optimisation is the cheapest, while the most expensive is the optimisation with emission function.

FIGURE 4.4: Emission and cost of associated EVs versus EV deployment scale averaged over 100 scenarios.

In Figure 4.4, we investigate the impact of the EV deployment scale. Figures 4.4a and 4.4b show the total emission and operational cost of associated EVs versus EV deployment scale. The low deployment scale represents rural areas with less EVs, while the high deployment scale represents their urban counterparts with much more EVs. As the deployment scale increases, the total emission and operational cost decreases, as seen in Figure 4.4a and 4.4b, respectively. This demonstrates that EVaaS system will be cheaper in urban areas, since more EVs are distributed closer to the CL. At all EV deployment scales, CEE optimisation produces the best performance.

FIGURE 4.5: Simulated sampling distribution of 100 scenarios.

Figure 4.5 shows the variation of 100 scenarios. It is to be noted that 100 scenarios are generated for each simulation setting (e.g., CL demand). At CL demand of 70 kWh, the mean and standard deviation of the emission data are 25.5 kg CO₂e and 2.6 kg CO₂e, respectively. While the mean and standard deviation of the operational cost data are £23.1 and £2.47, respectively. Figure 4.5a and Figure 4.5b were derived using a computational sampling approach to illustrate the normality in the distribution of the data from which we obtain our scenarios. The data are approximately normally distributed as depicted by the bell curve. This follows the central limit theorem which

FIGURE 4.6: Comparison of various schemes for different CL demand averaged over 100 scenarios.

establishes that the distribution of a sample mean will approach a normal distribution providing the sample size is sufficiently large. The normality in the distribution demonstrates the validity of the data.

In Figure 4.6, we compare the performance of our proposed optimisation strategy based on a greedy algorithm (GRA) with traditional strategies, considering knapsack algorithm (KPA) in [217] and FCFS scheme upon communication failure [214]. Figures 4.6a and 4.6b show the total emission and operational cost for fulfilling different CL demand. In the FCFS scheme, the CL sorts

geographic distances of EVs in a non-descending order, and selects EVs with shortest distance. While in KPA, the MGCC sorts costs in an ascending order and minimises the operating cost of fulfilling the CL demand. One hundred different scenarios were considered with respect to various CL demand, and for each scenario, the total emission and operational cost of associated EVs, and other parameters are used to compute the optimum association. The numerical results in Figure 4.6 show that GRA outperforms the FCFS scheme and KPA. In Figure 4.6a, the GRA produces 6% and 12% reduction in emissions for a CL demand of 40 kWh compared to KPA and FCFS scheme, respectively. Similarly, at CL demand of 60 kWh, the GRA produces a 5% and 9% improvement compared to KPA and FCFS scheme, respectively. While at every other CL demand, the GRA produces at least 2% and 4% improvement. In Figure 4.6b, between CL demand of 40 kWh and 80 kWh, the GRA produces at least 7% and 16% improvement compared to KPA and FCFS scheme, respectively. While at every other CL demand, the GRA reduces operational costs by at least 2% for KPA and 5% for FCFS scheme. Overall, we can observe that our proposed optimisation strategy achieves better capacity utilisation and significantly decreases emission and operational costs.

Figure 4.7 shows the energy and transportation costs for fulfilling CL demand using different resources and variety of tariffs that could impact the cost. At this stage, our analysis has variable tariffs for EV (mixed) and different fixed tariffs for the other resources. Figure 4.7a, 4.7b and 4.7c shows the energy and transportation costs for meeting low, medium and high CL demand, respectively, using DG, ESS, MEG, EV (mixed) and EV (eco). The DG and MEG costs are the amount it will cost to be supplied from a stationary and truck mounted DG at different CL demand, respectively. The ESS cost is the amount to be supplied from an ESS at the different CL demand. Fixed energy costs are assumed for utilizing the DG and ESS. Two types of EV resources

FIGURE 4.7: Cost for different CL demand using various resources.

are considered, the EV (eco) is for EVs assumed to have been charged with renewable energy, while the EV (mixed) is for EVs assumed to have charged from the grid. Different scenarios are considered and for each scenario, the variable energy and transportation tariffs of associated EVs and other parameters in Table 4.1 are used to compute the operational cost. The transportation cost increases with increase in CL energy demand, which can be seen in Figure 4.7b and 4.7c; this is because of the increase in number of associated EVs as seen in Figure 4.3. To cut down on the transportation cost, electric vans and buses (e.g., Tesla van with capacity of 90 kWh), can be considered. However, our optimisation model and analysis covers only passenger EVs. Fixed energy and transportation costs are assumed for the deployment of MEG using heavy goods vehicle. Table 4.1 presents parameters used to compute operational cost. Although the rental cost for the HGV used to transport the DG

FIGURE 4.8: Emissions for different CL demand using various resources.

has been excluded, the operating cost for deployment of MEG is still relatively high especially for low and medium CL demand. EVaaS reduces the total cost, thereby decreasing energy prices. Extreme events usually result in multiple line faults and this a limitation for the stationary DGs and ESSs. During contingencies, CL may be able to reach a feeder via undamaged tie lines. However, they cannot be fully restored due to operational constraints such as line flow limits. Therefore, EVs can play a key role in responding to contingencies.

Figure 4.8 shows the emissions for fulfilling CL demand using different resources and computed using their respective emission factors. The emission function (7) and other parameters in Table 4.1 are used to compute the emissions for EV (eco) and EV (mixed). The emission factors in [216] and other parameters in Table 4.1 are used to compute the emissions for the other resources using (5). EV (eco) is for EVs assumed to have charged from RESs such as wind turbines and solar photovoltaic systems, while EV (mixed) is for

EVs assumed to have been charged from the electricity grid (energy mix). The carbon emissions from EVs charged directly from the electricity grid appears to be more than that of the other resources. This is because EVs charged from the electricity grid in countries that fossil fuel dominates their energy mix will have higher carbon footprint compared to EVs charged in countries that generate electricity from predominately renewable energy as seen in Figure 4.8. Furthermore, the carbon footprint of these EVs will exceed that of diesel/petrol vehicles and traditional DERs. Unlike conventional vehicles, EVs do not produce any exhaust emission and powering CL with EVs charged from predominantly renewable energy reduces emissions remarkably as seen in Figure 4.8. Also, the power quality from RESs can be significantly improved by using EVs as storage and filter devices. Thus, the combination of EVs and RESs makes the microgrid greener and improves stability, reliability and resilience. The GHG emissions from EVs is small compared with other DERs, and thus does not impede the transition towards climate friendly back-up power supply.

4.5 Summary

This chapter proposed a combined economic emission resource allocation framework for selecting physically distant EVs to fulfil CL demand. The EVaaS system is modelled considering EV battery degradation cost and the feasibility of the system is discussed. The CEE optimisation problem is formulated considering energy demand, cost budget, emission limit and charging station limit constraints. Illustrative cases demonstrate the effectiveness and greenness of EVaaS and by charging from predominantly renewable sources, EVs diminishes environmental pollution significantly. Compared to traditional DERs, EVaaS is cost effective for short-term demand and supply balancing in the

microgrids and can be better utilised for resilient emergency response. The next chapter jointly investigates the energy cost and radio usage of discharging EVs in V2G communication networks.

Chapter 5

Resource Efficient

Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G)

Communication Systems

5.1 Introduction

This chapter presents a resource efficiency (RE) optimisation model that jointly considers energy cost and radio usage in Vehicle-to-grid (V2G) communication networks. The resource efficiency exploits the trade-off between spectral efficiency (SE) and cost efficiency (CE) of discharging electric vehicles (EVs). The economic aspect in Chapter 3 is examined through CE. This chapter is based on results in [114] and addresses the fifth research question of this thesis. V2G systems require a tightly controlled spectrum for reliable communication between electric vehicles (EVs) and the microgrid through the base station (BS) [222]. The system would need information about EVs such as battery capacity, energy price and location information to intelligently

manage the energy resources distributed within the local region. Transmitting this information over efficient wireless communication links is a crucial requirement for successful V2G interaction.

5.1.1 Background

The standard protocols for communication over long distances in vehicular networks are IEEE 802.11p and WiMAX technologies [6]. The IEEE 802.11p standard and mobile WiMAX (based on IEEE 802.16e standard) have been investigated as a media for vehicular communication [112, 113]. IEEE 802.11p technology is the popular standard for vehicular networks, offering a coverage area of up to 1km, data rates of up to 54 Mbps and latency as low as 50 ms. On the other hand, WiMAX technology possess similar features as IEEE 802.11p but offers longer range communication of up to 5km, higher data transfer speed of up to 100 Mbps and very low delays between 25-40 ms, which is suitable for V2G applications. The mobility mode of WiMAX standard is based on orthogonal frequency-division multiple access (OFDMA) that provides flexibility in radio resource management (RRM) and robustness against adverse effects of multipath fading. With OFDMA, exclusive channel assignment eliminates intracell interference, in which subchannels are allotted to a maximum of one EV in each cell at any given time [223].

RRM plays a major role in the performance of vehicular communication networks [224, 225]. The nature of the vehicular communication links based on the radio channel and the access to the shared resources causes variable available bandwidth, latency and data rate. This could prevent the correct operation of V2G applications. The V2G network needs to be fast and efficient in order to support the increasing number of EVs expected to participate in V2G. SE is one of the key performance metrics in the design and optimisation

of wireless communication networks. It is an essential performance metric for evaluating the effectiveness of V2G networks. CE is another performance indicator which measures the data rate of the V2G channel between EVs and BS over the operating cost of EVs expected to supply energy to critical loads (CLs). Optimizing the SE does not actualise a cost-efficient V2G system, likewise, cost-effective optimisation does not achieve a spectrum-efficient V2G communication link. Hence, taking CE into consideration while achieving SE is both challenging and desirable.

A number of recent works have focused on the use of wireless communication between EVs and the microgrid for V2G management [20–27]. An EV based V2G integrating virtual plant architecture is outlined in [20]. The study is focused on the V2G communication requirement to gather data from EVs, the electricity grid, energy generators, and other grid subsystems as well as to communicate with EVs for control purposes. In [21], a framework for enabling IP communications in mobile V2G environments is introduced. The technologies, block components and protocols needed for IPV6 support in V2G communications were specified. A smart charging management system for EVs charging station is proposed in [22], which consists of a centralised management system and single-node charging controllers. The system obtains charging data and transmits control instructions to the BS via GPRS and Zig-Bee. An EV charging scheduling scheme is developed in [23], considering the impact of data communication unavailability on the scheduling performance of a charging station. An optimisation problem is then formulated and solved for an optimal policy that minimises the cost due to performance degradation and power consumption.

In [24], two IEEE 802.11p-based quality of service schemes that enable EVs and smart grid interaction are presented for EV charging coordination and control. Using access points, informed decision can be taken on which EV

receives highest priority to access the communication link based on EV battery level, and availability and electricity cost at different charging stations. In [25], the average delay time for a group of charging EVs covered by one access point is modeled, based on Markov chain representation for the wireless IEEE 802.11 MAC protocol. The model further considers the effect of a lossy wireless link between charging EVs and the access point and its impact on the delay. An EV charging management scheme utilizing vehicular communication between EVs and access points based on IEEE 1609 WAVE and IEC 61850 standards is proposed in [26]. Using data obtained from participating EVs and by implementing a smart scheduling scheme, EVs that critically need power supply are catered for. A software-defined networking-based control scheme is developed in [27] for vehicular communication networks. The scheme obtains optimal association of vehicles with access points and further allocates appropriate transmission rates for both LTE and Wi-Fi communication to maximise the overall system quality of experience. Most contributions to RRM for V2G communication networks focus on EV charging coordination; to the best of our knowledge, the use of V2G communication for EV discharging management where EVs are associated with CL has not been studied in the literature in this context.

5.1.2 Our Contributions

This work is an extension of our work in [54], where the V2G communication network of the electric vehicle as a service (EVaaS) framework was not studied. In this chapter, we present an intelligent vehicular communication system to support EV interaction with the electricity grid. We focus on the RE optimisation which selects suitable EVs with efficient V2G communication links and operating costs for balancing short-term demand supply mismatch and

mitigating the severity of prolonged outages in a microgrid. EV data including location information, battery capacity and discharge efficiency, as well as CL location information and energy demand is needed for the association, which takes energy balance and charging station constraints into account. Charging stations are utilised as sources for associated EVs to provide power to the CL. The major contributions of this chapter are as follows.

- We propose RE to exploit the tradeoff between SE and CE of EVs associated with CLs, with a weighting coefficient controlling the balance between SE and CE. The RE is then formulated as an optimisation problem under CL energy demand and charging station constraints.
- The optimisation problem is known to be NP-hard, posing difficulties in finding the optimal solution. Towards solving this optimisation problem, we derive upper and lower bounds to the optimal RE. We then develop a less complex suboptimal scheme, based on a two-phase algorithm, to solve the proposed RE problem. For a fixed transmit power allocation, phase 1 finds the optimal EV-CL association using a heuristic approach, and subsequently, with this obtained EV-CL association solution, phase 2 derives the optimum transmit power allocation solution using geometric programming (GP).
- Simulation results demonstrate that the strategy is effective in matching EV with CL on demand, thus achieving better utilisation of EV battery capacity. Numerical results reveal that the proposed suboptimal scheme is close to the optimal solution, while its complexity is relatively low, making it applicable to V2G wireless communication networks and particularly promising to EVaaS application.

The remainder of the chapter is organised as follows. In section 5.2, the system model is described, as well as the spectral-efficient and cost-efficient

only designs. We formulate the resource efficiency optimisation problem in section 5.3. In section 5.4, we derive an upper bound on the optimal solution to jointly solve the optimisation problem. In section 5.5, a suboptimal scheme with low complexity is proposed, its algorithm explained and its computational complexity analysed. Simulation results and their analysis are provided in section 5.6, followed by concluding remarks in section 5.7.

5.2 System Model

5.2.1 System Description

The EVaaS system comprises of electrical and communication networks, however the latter is the system under study. The EVaaS communication network, as shown in Figure 5.1, consists of BS, EVs, CLs, microgrid central controller (MGCC) and smart meters. All EVs are connected with BS through dedicated V2G communication channels. We assume the wireless link between EVs and the BS is based on WiMAX standard. Meanwhile, each CL communicates with BS to gather the status information about EVs. Information regarding EV location or where it will be in the next time frame, the amount of time and available energy to transport EV to CL, the amount of energy that will be reserved for trading and subsequently transporting EV back to its destination or a suitable charging station are essential for scheduling EV with the CL. The smart meter measures electricity consumption and responds to remote command operations, while the MGCC facilitates the automated coordinated operation between EVs and CLs. The MGCC also carries out various functions including demand response activities, economical scheduling of charging/discharging EVs and forecasting studies.

FIGURE 5.1: EVaaS communication network consisting of a base station serving several electric vehicles.

We consider the downlink of a V2G communication network, where the coverage of a specific area is provided by a single BS. The sets of EVs, CLs and BS are denoted as $i = \{1, 2, \dots, I\}$, $j = \{1, 2, \dots, J\}$ and $k = \{1, 2, \dots, K\}$, respectively. The total available bandwidth, B_{tot} , is divided into N subchannels, with the bandwidth of the i th EV $b_i = (B_{tot}/N)$. With OFDMA, an exclusive channel assignment is assumed in each cell, i.e., subchannel cannot be assigned to more than one EV at any given time, to avoid interference among different EVs. It is to be noted that we investigate a scenario where the EVs are connected to a single serving base station at any given time and each BS optimises its resources as if it was insulated from the others. Therefore, we have assumed no intercell interference from neighbouring BSs. We assume that the distribution of BS, EVs and CLs does not change for time duration T (e.g., $T = 10$ ms), and thus we study their association considering the active EVs during the time interval $[0 T]$.

The propagation channel between BS to EV is subject to Rayleigh fading, log-normal shadowing and a distant dependent path loss. We denote the channel gain between BS and EV as H_i , which is modelled as $H_i = |h_i|^2 d_{ik}^{-\xi}$, where

$|h_i|^2$ denotes the composite channel gain between BS and EV due to Rayleigh fading and log-normal shadowing, ξ is the path-loss exponent, and d_{ik} is the distance between the k th BS and i th EV.

We denote the transmit power allocated to the i th EV over the V2G channel as p_i . Assuming full channel information is known at the BS and EV, the received signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) at the i th EV is expressed as:

$$\gamma_i(p_i) = \left(\frac{p_i H_i}{N_0 b_i} \right), \quad (5.1)$$

where N_0 is the noise spectral density. Without loss of generality, noise spectral density is assumed to be equal for all EVs. It will be recalled that there is no interference among EVs due to assumption of OFDMA. The data rate of the i th EV can be calculated by Shannon capacity formula as

$$r_i(p_i) = b_i \log_2(1 + \gamma_i(p_i)). \quad (5.2)$$

5.2.2 Performance Metrics

5.2.2.1 Spectral Efficiency

The SE refers to the data rate transmitted over the V2G channel between EVs and BS over the bandwidth of the EVs. The SE of the i th EV can be written as

$$SE_i = \frac{r_i(p_i)}{b_i}. \quad (5.3)$$

5.2.2.2 Cost Efficiency

The CE refers to the data rate of the V2G channel between EVs and BS over the operating cost of EVs expected to supply energy to CLs. The operating cost is the total amount to deploy discharging EVs in a microgrid to supply CLs. The operating cost here includes the energy cost and the transportation cost to CL from the current location of EVs. The energy cost should cover the charge cost and compensate battery related losses incurred during during EV-CL interaction, to avoid making financial losses from EVaaS participation. Similarly, the transportation cost should cover transportation related liabilities. Factors used to calculate transportation fares include cost of vehicle parts, labour, road tax, insurance, fuel (energy) and average energy consumption rate (0.2 kWh per km) [226]. Considering these factors, we have assumed a transportation tariff for participating EVs. The operating cost is formulated as

$$C_{ij} = EC_i v_{ij} + TC_i d_{ij}, \quad (5.4)$$

where v_{ij} denotes the amount of energy of the i th EV, in kWh, which is the on-demand battery capacity vc_i multiplied by the discharge efficiency ef_i of the battery ($v_{ij} = vc_i \cdot ef_i$); EC_i denotes the unit energy cost of the i th EV, measured in British Pounds (£) per kWh; TC_i denotes the unit transportation cost of the i th EV, measured in British Pounds (£) per km; d_{ij} denotes the estimated transportation distance between the i th EV and j th CL, in km.

The CE, measured in bits per second/British Pounds (£), can be written as

$$CE_{ij} = \frac{r_i(p_i)}{C_{ij}}. \quad (5.5)$$

5.3 Resource Efficiency Problem Formulation

The RE exploits the tradeoff between SE and CE. The objective of the optimisation problem is to maximise the two objective functions, SE and CE, while satisfying all inequality and equality constraints. Considering the inconsistency of metric units for CE and SE, it is inappropriate to directly add CE and SE. Moreover, a simple summation of CE and SE will tend to focus the optimisation problem on CE, since the operating cost C_{ij} is numerically smaller than the bandwidth b_i . Just as in the previous chapter, we use the weighted sum method for simplicity. Similar to [227], we now introduce a normalisation constant $\beta' = \beta(B_{tot}/C_{tot})$, where B_{tot}/C_{tot} acts as unit normaliser for SE and CE, while the weight factor β controls the balance of SE and CE.

Hence, the RE can be defined as

$$RE_{ij} = \frac{r_i(p_i)}{C_{ij}} \left(1 + \beta \frac{\eta_C}{\eta_B} \right), \quad (5.6)$$

where η_C and η_B denotes operating cost utilisation and bandwidth utilisation, respectively, given by

$$\eta_C = \frac{C_{ij}}{C_{tot}}, \quad \eta_B = \frac{b_i}{B_{tot}}. \quad (5.7)$$

By substituting (5.7) in (5.6), we have

$$RE_{ij} = CE_{ij} + \beta' SE_i. \quad (5.8)$$

Notably, due to normalisation factor B_{tot}/C_{tot} , the unit of the proposed RE is bps/£, which is still the same as CE. On the other hand, the weight between CE and SE is β , such that the RE will optimise CE when $\beta = 0$, while SE will

be optimised when $\beta = \infty$. Choosing appropriate weight is then up to the decision maker, since there is no a priori correspondence between a solution vector and a weight vector [227]. Therefore, without loss of generality, β is considered as a constant in our RE optimisation problem.

Consider the system shown in Figure 5.1, where EVs, CLs and BS are independently and identically distributed in a square region of area A_r . We model their locations as a binomial point process (BPP) [207]. This provides uniformly distributed random points of EVs, CLs and BS denoted as (x_i, y_i) , (x_j, y_j) and (x_k, y_k) , respectively. From the fixed positions of EVs, CLs and BS, the distance $d_{ij} = |x_i - x_j| + |y_i - y_j|$ between i th EV and j th CL and distance $d_{ik} = \sqrt{(x_i - x_k)^2 + (y_i - y_k)^2}$ between i th EV and k th BS is derived.

The association between EVs and CLs is constrained by some limiting factors, and would vary with changes in these factors. Hence, out of the available EV-CL pairs only few can be associated. The following discussion introduces the limiting factors of the system and then formulates the association problem of EVs and CLs based on those factors. α_{ij} is an entry of $(I \times J)$ association matrix α that defines the association of EVs and CLs as follows:

$$\alpha_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } i\text{th EV is assigned to } j\text{th CL,} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (5.9)$$

The objective is to maximise the RE of EVs serving CL demand, provided they have available energy and are connected over efficient V2G communication links. The generalised RE optimisation problem can be formulated as

$$\max_{\alpha_{ij}, p_i} \sum_{i=1}^I \sum_{j=1}^J \alpha_{ij} \frac{r_i(p_i)}{C_{ij}} \left(1 + \beta \frac{\eta_C}{\eta_B} \right) \quad (5.10)$$

Subject to

$$\sum_{i=1}^I \alpha_{ij} v_{ij} \geq V_j, \forall j \quad (5.10a)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^I p_i \leq P_{max} \quad (5.10b)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^I \alpha_{ij} \leq CS_j, \forall j \quad (5.10c)$$

$$\sum_{i=j}^J \alpha_{ij} \leq 1, \forall i. \quad (5.10d)$$

The energy supplied by the EVs must satisfy CL demand and the system losses, however there is no loss of load being considered. This can be written as constraint (5.10a), where the sum available energy from associated EVs v_{ij} equals or exceeds the CL demand V_j . Since the total transmit power of the BS is nonnegative and limited, the sum transmit power to all associated EVs is constrained by constraint (5.10b), where P_{max} denotes the maximum transmit power at the base station for downlink transmission. Constraint (5.10c) shows that j th CL can maintain a maximum number of discharging EVs as per charging station limit CS_j . Constraint (5.10d) imposes that each EV can be associated to a maximum of one CL.

5.4 Optimal Resource Efficiency Schemes

The optimisation problem introduced in (5.10) is a combinatorial mixed-integer non-linear programming (MINLP) problem. It has a non-convex objective function and involves non-linear constraints with binary and continuous

variables, i.e. α_{ij} and p_i , respectively. That is to say, (5.10) is a general NP-hard optimisation problem. Therefore, even for small set-ups, it is generally very hard to solve the original problem in reasonable time based on branch-and-bound or exhaustive search techniques. Thus, we propose a decomposition of the original MINLP problem into a mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) and a non-linear programming (NLP) problem. The MILP problem associates optimum EVs with CL, while the NLP problem derives the optimum transmit power allocation over the V2G communication network. Considering this approach, solutions can be obtained in desired computational times as discussed next.

5.4.1 Optimal Resource Efficiency in High Signal to Noise Regime

The optimal solution for (5.10) can be computed in the high SNR regime by an exhaustive search over all possible combination of the association, assuming perfect knowledge of channel gains at MGCC. For each possible association, optimum transmit powers can be computed by transforming (5.10) into a GP [228]. It should be noted that transmit power allocation problem is in itself a known non-convex problem for the general SNR regime [229]. But in a high SNR regime, it can be reformulated as a convex GP problem where the objective is to minimise a posynomial. For a fixed set of association variables and considering a high SNR regime, the objective function in (5.10) can be rewritten as follows

$$\max_{p_i} \sum_{i=1}^I \sum_{j=1}^J \alpha_{ij} \log_2 \left(\frac{p_i H_i}{N_0 b_i + \psi} \right) \left(\frac{1}{C_{ij}} + \frac{\beta}{C_{ij}} \frac{\eta_C}{\eta_B} \right). \quad (5.11)$$

Maximising the SNR is equivalent to minimising the noise-to-signal ratio

$$\min_{p_i} \sum_{i=1}^I \sum_{j=1}^J \alpha'_{ij} \log_2 \left(\frac{N_0 b_i + \psi}{p_i H_i} \right), \quad (5.12)$$

where $\alpha'_{ij} = \alpha_{ij} \left(\frac{1}{C_{ij}} + \frac{\beta}{C_{ij}} \frac{\eta_C}{\eta_B} \right)$ and ψ is a constant. Equivalently, (5.12) can be reformulated for high SNR regime as follows

$$\min_{p_i} \log_2 \prod_{i=1}^I \prod_{j=1}^J \left(\frac{N_0 b_i + \psi}{p_i H_i} \right)^{\alpha'_{ij}} \quad (5.13)$$

subject to: 5.10b.

Note that the denominator in (5.13) is a monomial and the numerator is a posynomial. The ratio of a posynomial to a monomial is also a posynomial. The problem formulated in (5.13) is a GP problem in standard form that can be solved optimally through efficient interior point methods [230] after performing the logarithmic transformation of variables [229]. This will be used later on to derive optimum transmit power allocation. Due to extreme high computational complexity associated with exhaustive search-based EV-CL association phase, it is not recommended to compute the optimal solution. Additionally, the GP-based transmit power allocation is restricted by high SNR assumption and centralised time-consuming computations. In respect to the aforementioned facts, developing bounds and suboptimal RE schemes with reasonable computational complexity is desirable.

5.4.2 Upper Bound on the Optimal Resource Efficiency

An alternative approach to make the problem (5.10) more tractable is to use linear programming relaxation. This relaxation technique has been frequently

used in the context of subchannel assignment in multiuser OFDMA systems to convert mixed-integer programming problems into convex optimisation problems [227, 231–234]. Unlike the previous definition where $\alpha_{ij} \in \{0, 1\}$ indicates whether the i th EV is associated to the j th CL, we need to relax the binary constraint on the association matrix α_{ij} as

$$0 \leq \alpha_{ij} \leq 1, \quad (5.14)$$

so the entries of the association matrix are continuous and can vary between 0 and 1. The fractional α_{ij} can be interpreted as time domain sharing of charging stations at the CL. The sharing factor converts (5.10) into a convex optimisation problem, as illustrated in the following:

$$\max_{\alpha_{ij}, p_i} \sum_{i=1}^I \sum_{j=1}^J \alpha_{ij} \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{p_i H_i}{\alpha_{ij} N_0 b_i} \right) \left(\frac{1}{C_{ij}} + \frac{\beta}{C_{ij}} \frac{\eta_C}{\eta_B} \right) \quad (5.15)$$

subject to: 5.10a - 5.10d.

Evidently, by relaxing α_{ij} as (5.14) and reformulating the RE objective function in (5.15), the RE optimisation problem produces an upper bound on the RE of (5.10), although it does not always yield a solution where α_{ij} is either 0 or 1. Recall that C4 along with the binary condition (5.9) previously restricted each EV to be associated to a maximum of one CL only. This relaxation allows for the association problem to be solved using standard convex optimisation techniques [235]. The complexity of the solution of (5.15) is comparably high to apply in practical V2G communication systems. More importantly, the solution of (5.15) is infeasible because the sharing factor α_{ij} (continuous between 0 and 1) means that an EV can be associated to multiple CLs, which is not the case of our considered problem, according to constraint (5.10d). However,

we can take the solution as an upper bound of the optimisation problem (5.10) to benchmark the performance of the other schemes.

5.5 Suboptimal Resource Efficiency Schemes

Convex programming is numerically stable but its computational complexity relies on the number of optimisation variables, which can be large if the number of EVs and CLs are large. To tackle the computational complexity of the proposed optimisation problem in (5.10), we split the procedure into two phases: EV-CL association phase and transmit power allocation phase. In phase 1, for a given transmit power allocation, the association matrix considered as the variable of the optimisation problem is solved. This derived association matrix is then used in Phase 2 to find the corresponding allocated transmit power as the solution to the transmit power allocation optimisation problem. Note that the EV-CL association phase involves an equal transmit power allocation step; thus, it is not totally independent of transmit power allocation.

5.5.1 EV-CL Association

Considering a fixed transmit power p , with uniform transmit power allocation scheme, the maximum achievable RE is defined as

$$\max_{\alpha_{ij}} \sum_{i=1}^I \sum_{j=1}^J \alpha_{ij} \frac{r_i(p_i)}{C_{ij}} \left(1 + \beta \frac{\eta_C}{\eta_B} \right) \quad (5.16)$$

subject to: 5.10a - 5.10d.

In (5.16), the only optimisation variable is α , hence, (5.16) has less computational complexity compared to (5.10). When the optimal solution of (5.16) is found, EVs that offer the highest RE are assigned to the CLs. We can take the solution of (5.16) as the lower bound to measure the performance of other algorithms.

5.5.2 Transmit Power Allocation

Considering a fixed association matrix α , the maximum achievable RE at a certain maximum transmit power, P_{max} , is as follows

$$\max_{p_i} \sum_{i=1}^I \sum_{j=1}^J \alpha_{ij} \frac{r_i(p_i)}{C_{ij}} \left(1 + \beta \frac{\eta_C}{\eta_B} \right) \quad (5.17)$$

subject to: 5.10b.

We solve the problem in (5.17) to find out the optimal transmit power through GP (5.13) using successive convex approximation. The target of the transmit power allocation is to ensure that associated EVs achieve better performance.

5.5.3 Optimisation Algorithm

We propose an algorithm that finds the EV-CL association and transmit power allocation for each EV in a V2G communication network. To implement the algorithm, a central processing unit is needed to collect all the network information and perform the optimisation. The proposed strategy is to choose EVs with the maximum RE. The algorithm starts with computing I EVs, J CLs and K BS and their distribution in a defined area. A snap shot of EVs,

Algorithm 5.1 EV-CL Association and Transmit Power Allocation

Input: $I, J, V, CS, v_{ij}, p_i = P_{max}/I, \alpha_{ij} = 0$ **Output:** α **EV-CL Association (Phase I)**

- 1: Make a list of EVs, CLs and BS within the Area A_r
- 2: Calculate the distance d_{ij} between EVs and CLs and d_{ik} between EVs and BS.
- 3: Compute p_i by dividing P_{max} equally among the EVs.
- 4: Using p_i from step 3, compute data rate r_i for the i th EV.
- 5: Initialise counters: $C_{CS} = 0$ and $C_V = 0$
- 6: **while** list of CLs to EVs is not empty **do**
- 7: For a fixed p_i , find optimal EV-CL association in (5.16).
- 8: **if** $C_V + v_{ij} \geq V$ **then**
- 9: **if** $C_{CS} \leq CS$ **then**
- 10: Update $\alpha_{ij} = 1, C_{CS} = C_{CS} + 1$ and $C_V = C_V + v_{ij}$
- 11: Remove other links of selected EV i from the list
- 12: **else**
- 13: Remove all links of j th CL from the list
- 14: **end if**
- 15: **else**
- 16: **break**
- 17: **end if**
- 18: **end while**

Transmit Power Allocation (Phase II)

- 19: For a fixed α_{ij} , find the optimum transmit power allocation according to (5.17) using CVX [230, 235].
 - 20: Compute data rate r_i for the i th EV and update RE of associated EVs.
-

CLs and BS is then obtained providing their respective distribution points (x_i, y_i) , (x_j, y_j) and (x_k, y_k) , which is then used to derive the distance d_{ij} between i th EV and j th CL and the distance d_{ik} between i th EV and k th BS. The EV capacity v_{ij} is also obtained, along with the CL demand V_j and number of charging stations CS_j .

For the first phase, transmit power is divided equally over all EVs in the network. Two counters are initialised; energy demand of CLs C_V and maximum number of charging stations C_{CS} . Out of the list of EV to CL links, the link that provides the optimal EV-CL association is selected. The algorithm then

Algorithm 5.2 Closet EV-CL Association Algorithm

Input: $I, J, V, CS, v_{ij}, p_i = P_{max}/I, \alpha_{ij} = 0$

Output: α

- 1: Repeat steps 1 to 6 of Algorithm 5.1
 - 2: Sort d_{ij} in ascending order and find closet EV-CL association.
 - 3: Repeat steps 8 to 18 of Algorithm 5.1
 - 4: For a fixed α_{ij} , derive the optimum transmit power allocation from Algorithm 1.
 - 5: Compute data rate r_i for the i th EV and update RE of associated EVs.
-

verifies the constraints of energy balance $C1$ and number of charging stations $C3$ such that $C_V + v_{ij} \geq V$ and $C_{CS} + 1 \leq CS$, respectively. If all requirements are satisfied, the selected EV-CL pair is associated by modifying the association matrix entry as $\alpha = 1$ and the respective counters are updated accordingly. The process repeats until the list ends or the resources ends that can be tracked using the two counters. Then, for a fixed association matrix α , the optimal transmit power allocation (5.17) is found using GP (5.13). This is used to compute the data rate and update the RE of associated EVs. The steps are summarised in Algorithm 5.1.

We also consider a scenario where CL applies a predefined policy to select EVs with shortest geographic distance. This approach could be adopted during data communication unavailability from the MGCC. Since the decision making is always based on updated information, the system relies on the MGCC to develop effective optimal EV-CL association decision. However, issues related to transmission failure are usually inevitable. If optimum EV-CL association is not obtained from the system, the CL would select EVs with shortest distance as a backup scheme [214]. EVs are then associated with the CL based on first come first served (FCFS) scheme. In the FCFS scheme, the CL sorts the distances between EVs and CLs in an ascending order, and selects EVs that are closet to the CL. The strategy for the FCFS scheme is similar to Algorithm 5.1, with exception in the first phase. This is summarised in Algorithm 5.2.

5.5.4 Computational Complexity

Complexity plays a vital role in resource-efficient decision-making systems. Computations are performed in a centralised fashion, where a central controller has knowledge of the channel of all EVs and current association. Considering the size of problem (5.10) in our numerical analysis, it is not practical to find the optimal solution by any existing method. The global optimisation method [213], which is applicable to small-scale problems, would take an impractical amount of time to return a global optimum of the transmit power allocation problem (5.17). We examine the computational complexity of our proposed algorithm considering float operations. At the first step, when EV is associated to a CL through linear search in (5.16), the association matrix can be formed with a complexity of $O(IJ)$. The while loop of the algorithm will terminate when the scheme defines the optimal i th EV. When calculating the optimum transmit power allocation at the second step, the complexity is of $O(I \log_2 I)$. Thus, the total complexity of our proposed algorithm is of $O(IJ \log_2 I)$.

Considering [213], the computational complexity of the optimal solution (5.10) is significantly higher than that of our suboptimal scheme. Additionally, to the best of our knowledge, there is no other suboptimal solution available in previous related works that solves (5.10). Therefore, we limit our simulation study to demonstrating the performances of Algorithm 5.1 and Algorithm 5.2 and comparing the solutions in the upper bound and lower bound schemes.

5.6 Simulation Results and Discussions

We consider an EvaaS communication network where EVs, CLs and BS are BPP distributed within a $4 \text{ km} \times 4 \text{ km}$ area. We assume there are $I =$

FIGURE 5.2: Impact of weighted factor β to the corresponding SE and CE.

12 EVs and $J = 2$ CLs, unless otherwise stated. In the BS, we assume OFDMA downlink transmission with $K = 32$ subchannels, each of which has a bandwidth of 15 kHz. The channel gains are derived by the Rayleigh fading model, where the path loss ξ is set equal to 4 and h_i is the exponential random variable with mean/parameter equal to 1. The maximum transmit power P_{max} of BS is considered to be 1 W, unless otherwise stated, and noise spectral density is chosen as -174 dBm/Hz. Battery capacity between 15 kWh and 28 kWh and discharging efficiency between 0.90 and 0.95 are randomly assigned to EVs. Unit energy tariff between £0.07/kWh and £0.12/kWh and unit transportation tariff between £0.8/km and £1.3/km are randomly assigned to EVs. Energy demand between 20 kWh and 200 kWh is uniformly allocated to CLs. Considering the data of the EVs, CLs and BS, with battery capacity and coordinates for EVs, energy demand and coordinates for CLs, EvaaS communication network information and other parameters, the parameters for EV to CL association is computed. The necessary parameters are then passed to the algorithms to find the best possible association between EVs and CLs by maximising the optimisation problem (5.10).

FIGURE 5.3: The layout of random distribution and association of EVs and CLs with constraints $V = 60$ kWh, $CS = 3$.

We present in Figure 5.2 the impact of weighted factor β to the corresponding SE and CE. Clearly, as the weight factor β increases, the SE decreases, while the corresponding CE increases as the weight factor β increases. Recall that RE focuses on optimizing CE when the value of β is small, while the focus shifts to SE when the value β is large. The reason is that an increase in β results to putting more weight on SE, thus more resources (data rate and bandwidth) are allocated for SE maximisation. Specifically, when $\beta = 0.8$, the corresponding CE and SE are close to the maximum CE (when $\beta = 0$) and maximum SE (when $\beta = \infty$), with the amount of degradation being 2% and 3% on CE and SE, respectively. This can be seen as justification for the

FIGURE 5.4: Comparison of all proposed schemes for different CL demand.

proposed use of B_{tot}/C_{tot} as the normalisation factor in the RE formulation. Consequently, we set β to 0.8 for the remainder of the simulation sections.

We optimise the same problem in (5.10) using different objective functions and study the performance of the objective function versus binary variable. Figure 5.3 presents a considered scenario of the the distribution and EV-CL association under the different objective functions. Figures 5.3a, 5.3b, 5.3c and 5.3d show EVs associated with CLs based on SE, operating cost, CE and RE, respectively. Although the same number of EVs are associated with CLs in Fig. 5.3, different EV-CL association are realised in all scenarios. This means the performance is different in each considered scenario, which we will analyze later in Figures 5.7 and 5.8. The case study verifies the capability of the formulations and proposed strategy to match suitable EVs with CLs, thus achieving better utilisation of the energy stored in EVs.

We then evaluate and compare the performances of all the proposed schemes. Figure 5.4 shows the comparison of the maximum achievable RE obtained by Algorithm 5.1, Algorithm 5.2, upper bound (5.15) and lower bound (5.16) for

FIGURE 5.5: Comparison of all proposed schemes for different maximum transmit power.

different CL demand from 20 kWh to 140 kWh. The first point to notice from Figure 5.4 is that the maximum achievable RE is increased with an increase in the CL demand. This can be attributed to the increasing number of associated EVs. It can also be noticed that Algorithm 5.1 considerably outperforms Algorithm 5.2 for different CL demand. It can be interpreted as Algorithm 5.1 achieves better capacity utilisation of EVs compared to Algorithm 5.2. In the absence of appropriate power allocation, the overall system performance will be impacted. The significance of the transmit power allocation phase can be observed easily from the performance gap between the Algorithm 5.1 and the lower bound. Algorithm 5.1 is close to the upper bound at certain CL demand. Specifically, Algorithm 5.1 results in a RE that is at least 91% of the upper bound RE. Although the upper bound is not ideal for our case study and reflects an over-optimistic RE, it provides an idea on the performance gap between the proposed schemes and the optimal solution.

We investigate the impact of different maximum transmit power P_{max} to the maximum achievable RE. Figure 5.5 shows the comparison of the maximum

FIGURE 5.6: Resource efficiency of associated EVs versus EV distribution density.

achievable RE obtained by Algorithm 5.1, Algorithm 5.2, and the upper and lower bounds for different maximum transmit power from 0.2 W to 2 W. As expected, with increasing maximum transmit power, the total maximum achievable RE also increases. However, there is a notably rise in the maximum achievable RE up to 1 W and then it slowly increases between 1.2 W and 2 W. This shows that much power can be saved by lowering the maximum transmit power, since increasing it does not necessarily guarantee the best maximum achievable RE to transmission power budget ratio.

We present in Figure 5.6 the impact of EV distribution density λ to the maximum achievable RE. Here, the number of EVs is a random variable. For a single value of density, we have generated 100 different scenarios and then averaged the maximum achievable RE obtained by Algorithm 1. The low density represents rural areas with less EVs, while the high density represents their urban counterparts with much more EVs. As the density increases, the maximum achievable RE increases, as seen in Figure 5.6. This demonstrates that the EVaaS system will achieve better RE in urban areas. Specifically,

FIGURE 5.7: Spectral efficiency of associated EVs for different CL demand.

FIGURE 5.8: Operating cost of associated EVs for different CL demand.

EVs will have better communication links and EVaaS applications will be cheaper, since more EVs are distributed closer to the CLs and BS. While the case study considers a microgrid with 2-4 CLs, the framework is general, and the extension is straight forward for multiple microgrids.

In Figures 5.7 and 5.8, we compare the EV-CL association based on SE, cost,

CE and RE functions. Figure 5.7 shows the SE for different CL demand. As expected, optimizing the SE function would typically give a better performance for SE. However, the RE optimisation produces a good trade off. The performance gap between the RE and CE functions is negligible, and they give nearly similar results, while the RE optimisation gives a better performance than optimizing the cost function. Figure 5.8 shows the operating cost for different CL demand. The cost optimisation would typically produce better results compared to the SE, CE and RE functions. At CL demand of 70 kWh and 90 kWh, the RE optimisation produces a 23% and 12% improvement, respectively, compared to the SE and CE functions. While at CL demand of 30 kWh, the RE optimisation produces a 30% improvement compared to the SE and CE functions. It is to be noted that the improvement by the RE optimisation is not specific to low or high CL demand. The performance gap can be attributed to the different EV-CL association realised from optimizing the different objective functions, as seen in Figure 5.3. Overall, optimisation considering RE function gives the best performance. Thus, the proposed RE better utilises the available resources in the EVaaS network.

5.7 Summary

In this chapter, we present an intelligent vehicular communication system to enable V2G interaction. We propose a resource efficiency framework for selecting suitable EVs to fulfil CL demand in V2G communication networks. The RE problem is formulated to maximise the spectral efficiency and cost efficiency, under CL energy demand and charging station constraints. In the proposed setup, EV-CL association and transmit power allocation are considered in a two-phase algorithm. Towards solving the proposed non-convex and NP-hard optimisation problem, we adopted an approach where in each

phase, one set of optimisation variables is derived. We also provide upper and lower bounds to the optimal RE as a benchmark to study the performance gap of the suboptimal scheme. Simulation results reveal that the performance of our proposed suboptimal scheme is close to the optimal solution, while the computational complexity is low, which makes it attractive for EVaaS applications.

Chapter 6

Conclusions and Future Work

6.1 Conclusions

This thesis has exploited V2G technology to develop a novel EVaaS framework for distribution networks, where EVs distributed within the microgrid are chosen to fulfil the energy demand of CL with respect to outage mitigation and peak demand fulfilment. The EVaaS framework achieves the first objective of the thesis. Based on this framework, the deployment of discharging EVs in the distribution network is investigated from three aspects: economic, emissions and communications.

In the economic aspect, an auction mechanism is proposed for incentivized energy trading between discharging EVs and CL in the distribution network. EV-CL association and discharging scheduling are considered in a two-phase model. In the first phase, EV-CL association is modeled as a single auction to determine the winning bids and corresponding payments. EV-CL association is formulated as an MINLP problem, where bidder satisfaction and transportation cost of physically distant EVs are considered. In the second phase,

EV discharging scheduling is modeled to determine the discharging power of associated EVs at each time slot. EV discharging scheduling is formulated as an operating cost minimisation problem which considers a number of practical constraints such as power balance, SoC and charging station limits. The operating cost includes the energy cost, transportation cost and battery degradation cost. The numerical results show that the proposed scheme achieves a performance which is comparable to those given by reference schemes, guarantees bidder satisfaction and validates theoretical analysis on economic properties of truthfulness and individual rationality. This model achieves the second objective of the thesis.

In the emissions aspect, a combined economic emission model is proposed to study the trade-off between emissions and energy cost in the distribution network. The combined economic emission problem is modeled as a bi-objective optimisation problem for optimum association of physically distant EVs with CL, with carbon price as the weighting factor. EV-CL association is formulated as an MINLP problem, considering a number of practical constraints, such as energy demand, cost budget, emission limit and charging station limit. Capacity loss and battery degradation were studied to ensure they do not become financial liabilities from V2G participation. The proposed model is compared with traditional strategies and distributed energy resources such as energy storage systems, diesel generator and mobile emergency generator. The feasibility of the proposed model is demonstrated in simulation studies and illustrative cases show the effectiveness and greenness of the proposed model. This model achieves the third objective of the thesis.

In the communications aspect, a resource efficiency model is proposed to study the trade-off between the spectral efficiency and cost efficiency of EVs in a V2G communication network. The cost efficiency is a performance indicator that measures the data rate of the V2G channel between EVs and base station over

the operating cost of discharging EVs. The resource efficiency is maximised in the downlink of a V2G communication network, where discharging EVs are served by a base station and associated with CLs. As the proposed problem is inherently non-convex and known to be NP-hard, a suboptimal scheme based on a two-phase algorithm is developed. Optimum EV-CL association is obtained using heuristic approach in the first phase, while optimum power allocation is derived using geometric programming in the second phase. An approach is adopted where in each phase, one set of optimisation variables is derived. Upper and lower bounds to the optimal resource efficiency are provided as a benchmark to study the performance of the suboptimal scheme. The simulation results show that the proposed scheme achieves a performance close to the optimal solution, while its complexity is relatively low, which makes it promising for V2G applications. This model achieves the fourth objective of the thesis.

6.2 Future Work

The energy management framework presented in this thesis improves the performance of the distribution system using EVs distributed over the local region. This study could be further developed in the following aspects:

Auction model: The energy trading process is modeled as a one-sided market with multiple EVs and a single CL, while the aggregator acts as an auctioneer. In future work, a double auction environment where multiple EVs and multiple CLs compete to sell and buy energy, respectively, will be considered. This two-sided market allows CLs to submit their bids (buy orders) and EVs to submit their asks (sell orders) to the auctioneer. The auctioneer then matches the orders to find the most efficient allocation and decides who

trades and at what prices. A cost-effective trading strategy can be adopted where trading entities are allowed to modify their bid/ask prices, amount of tradable energy and available trading time flexibly [236]. By enabling trading entities to bid/ask repeatedly, financial profits can be maximised via iterations. The double auction mechanism can be designed to achieve essential economic properties and the satisfaction level of buyers and sellers can be examined simultaneously, ensuring fairness in the energy trade.

V2G communication model: EV interaction with the electricity grid is not secure and private; therefore, EVs are exposed to tracking, profiling and data breach using their mobile IP address. Therefore, in the future, blockchain technology will be exploited to establish a trusted environment for V2G interaction [161]. A blockchain-based system will preserve the data of participating EVs using different privacy protection techniques. Additionally, 5G networks will be utilised to address the communication requirements of the system. 5G will provide more reliable communication for EVs, which is critical in managing the safety challenges associated with vehicle autonomy and automation [237]. V2X communication that is based on 5G will support autonomous energy trading, where parked EVs can charge and discharge their batteries to mitigate grid imbalance, while self-driving EVs can be routed to designated charging stations.

EV charging model: The EVaaS framework has covered several optimisation models for discharging EVs hoping to feed-back surplus energy to the distribution grid during peak demand or system failure. The framework will be extended to study EV charging optimisation and the challenges associated with deploying EVs to charge their batteries. The study would consider different EV charging scenarios. The first would be a scenario where the energy generated exceeds demand, example, during off-peak times or when there is excess production from RESs. The second would be a scenario where EV

charging adds to the pre-existing peak load on the distribution network, example, during fast charging. The emerging extreme fast and ultra-fast charging technologies hope to achieve comparable refueling time to that of ICE vehicles. With fast charging mostly occurring during the daytime, the utility would experience a significant increase in peak load. Smart charging strategies that consider current and future EV charging needs should be investigated.

EV mobility model: The study has considered an ideal mobility model where an average energy consumption rate is assumed for EVs. However, traffic, driving patterns, weather conditions, topography and other factors will influence the consumed SoC, transportation distance and EV arrival time. Thus, these uncertainties need to be addressed towards the implementation in practical scenarios. Realistic vehicular mobility models are required to properly estimate energy consumption of EVs. Simulation of Urban Mobility (SUMO) can be adopted to model vehicular environments [238]. Traffic dynamics on realistic road networks can be reproduced by micro-simulating the behaviour of EVs and roadside components such as traffic lights. Traffic loads can be generated based on macroscopic demographical data such as workplace density and number of inhabitants [239]. Electrical and mechanical dynamics that allow exploration of the regenerative braking characteristics of EVs can be simulated [240].

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